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**Dual-Lens Sensemaking in Higher Education Leadership Transition:
Integrating Weick's Theory and the Cynefin Framework**

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Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **JUVY M. CASIMERO** with the title: **“DUAL-LENS SENSEMAKING IN HIGHER EDUCATION LEADERSHIP TRANSITION: INTEGRATING WEICK’S THEORY AND THE CYNEFIN FRAMEWORK”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

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Biographical Sketch

Juvy M. Casimero was born on January 25, 1977, in Altavas, Aklan. He is an academic and communication professional whose career reflects a deep commitment to education.

He earned his Bachelor of Arts in Sociology and Broadcast Communication degree from the University of the Philippines in the Visayas and his Master of Development Communication from the University of the Philippines Open University.

Mr. Casimero served in various leadership capacities at Aklan State University. He was a former Director of University Curriculum where he drafted the university's curriculum policy and developed a handbook of inventory of curricular programs. He also served as Department Head of the Department of Communication, Languages, and Information Technology, and Program Chair of the Bachelor of Arts in Communication under the College of Arts and Sciences.

He was instrumental in the successful offering of the Bachelor of Arts in Communication program earning Certificate of Program Compliance (COPC) from CHED Region 6.

His leadership extend beyond academics having served as Project Coordinator of the Traditional Knowledge System (TKS) Project in Aklan. A project of the University of the Philippines in the Visayas funded by the DENR through the Office of Senator Loren Legarda. Further, he also served as a Project Leader of the Multimedia-Based Community Radio Project which aimed to restore the University's Community Radio - DYMT 100.9 FM Community Radio. The project was funded by the Department of Agriculture Region VI and CHED's Agri-Tourism project.

Currently, Mr. Casimero is still working in shaping the future of communication education at Aklan State University-Banga, Campus. His passion for communication

and its power to shape development and resilient communities serve as his continuing legacy.

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Dedication

This work is dedicated to myself for not giving up despite
unavoidable circumstances.

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Abstract

This convergent parallel mixed-methods study used dual-lens framework aimed at determining sensemaking engagement, examining contextual sensemaking triggers, exploring the interpretation of leadership transition, and identifying emerging constructs expanding the sensemaking framework. Quantitative surveys and qualitative narratives were collected from 26 middle managers from a Philippine state university.

Quantitative results showed strong sensemaking engagement through retrospection, ongoing process, and plausibility that showed respondents' preference for coherence, dialogue, and trust. Narrative analysis, referenced with the Cynefin framework, revealed shifting domains from Clear or Chaotic toward Complex domain where negation and collaboration were necessary to maintain institutional alignment. Further, using Weick's sensemaking properties, seven themes were generated by Reflexive Thematic Analysis - *Identity as an Adaptive Self, Retrospection as Negotiated Reality, Situated Intentional Action, Collaboration through Dialogue as Core the Core of Sensemaking, Sensemaking as an Ongoing Engagement, Cues as Cornerstone of Meaning Construction, and Plausibility as Pragmatic Truth.*

The integration of contextual and interpretive dimensional frameworks refined sensemaking scholarship by advancing the idea of adaptative sensemaking and collaborative actions as theoretical enhancements in dealing with uncertainty during leadership transition in an academic context.

Keywords: dual-lens sensemaking, adaptive sensemaking, collaborative actions, Cynefin framework in leadership transition, sensemaking in higher education

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Leadership transition is not simply transferring authority and responsibility from a departing head of institution to the new head; it implies change of organizational landscape for state universities in the Philippines. Described as the critical stage, it suggests new strategic directions, priorities, and operational standards. This transition influences governance, decision-making, and over-all structure of the academic institutions.

During this transition, ambiguity surfaces creating confusions among mid-level university officials who are confronted with shifting roles, uncertain expectations, and unclear directions. These officials, who by function serves as middle managers between the institutional leadership and the frontline employees, are tasked to interpret and clarify information which are vague or inadequately articulated. Their roles are not only confined to cascading information; but demands reframing, negotiating, and contesting administrative and academic directives. The absence of a clear and comprehensible interpretation from these managers creates institutional disconnect during the transition.

The application of sensemaking in higher education provides a practical understanding of how change is manage. Karl Weick (1995) defined sensemaking as a method of creating meaning in complex, ambiguous, and rapidly changing environment. It works as a tool and strategic framework to aid interpretations and direct group actions. Further to this approach is Dave Snowden's Cynefin Framework (2007) which divided organizational context into contextual categories - clear,

complicated, complex, chaotic, and disorder. These two theoretical frameworks allow a more dynamic understanding of how uncertainties are managed during the transition.

Despite the substantial body of sensemaking literatures, the majority of these studies focused on Western or corporate contexts (Maitlis & Christianson, 2014; Weick et al., 2005). A considerable gap exists in the study involving higher education institutions in the Global South. This study fills this gap by exploring how middle managers make sense during leadership transition in a state university in the Philippines. It specifically explores sensemaking engagement, contextual triggers of sensemaking, interpretive dimension of sensemaking, and emerging constructs extending sensemaking scholarship using an integrated framework as a dual-lens approach.

The study contributes to the understanding of sensemaking being applied to organizational change in higher education institutions. This provides a non-Western academic environment where sensemaking is contextualized as a theoretical framework.

Statement of the Problem

Leadership transition in higher education usually results to institutional changes creating uncertainties. These ambiguities expose employees to confusing expectations, shifting roles, and more often, inconsistent communication. Among those affected are middle managers who find it difficult to understand institutional goals which are either new or are not well articulated.

This study explored how middle managers use sensemaking as a strategy and method to manage and understand leadership change. The study combined Cynefin Framework (Snowden & Boone, 2007) and Sensemaking Theory (Weick, 1995) to

analyze contextual triggers of sensemaking and to interpret how they comprehended and responded to institutional change.

Specifically, the study addressed the following research questions:

1. What is the extent of middle managers' engagement in sensemaking during leadership transition?
2. How do contextual conditions prompt middle managers to engage in sensemaking?
3. How do middle managers interpret leadership transition?
4. What emerging constructs can be identified from the integrated findings of the study that extend existing theoretical frameworks?

Objectives of the Study

To systematically address the research questions, this study was structured around the following objectives:

1. Measure the extent of middle managers' engagement in sensemaking processes during leadership transition.
2. Examine how contextual conditions prompt middle managers to make sense.
3. Explore middle managers' interpretation of leadership transition.
4. Identify emerging constructs extending sensemaking framework.

Significance of the Study

The study contributes to the literatures on sensemaking particularly on meaning-making during leadership transition in higher education. Despite abundance of researches on structural reforms, policy changes, or leadership styles (Maitlis &

Christianson, 2014; Gioia & Chittipeddi, 1991), there were few studies documenting the interpretive processes and meaning-making during leadership transition.

The findings of this study has practical implications for research scholarship, change management, institutional planning, and leadership development especially for higher education leaders.

Middle Managers in Higher Education. This study provides framework and practices that could enhance knowledge in dealing with future leadership transition and provide them an in-depth understanding of their roles to making sure alignment and stability are maintained during organizational changes.

Higher Education Institutions. This study will help higher education institutions identify weak points in communicating change within the organization to maintain trust, legitimacy, and continuity.

Researchers. The study extends and refines the theoretical frameworks on sensemaking through an integrative lens to examine organizational change especially in education.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study explored university middle managers sensemaking during a leadership transition in a Philippine state university. Using Sensemaking Theory (1995) and Cynefin Framework (2007), the study looked at how they use sensemaking as a strategy and approach to understanding leadership change.

The study focused on middle-level managers (vice presidents, directors, deans, and department heads) whose functional roles involved interpreting and implementing institutional directives while facilitating communication between executive leadership and organizational members. Specifically, it examined the extent of their sensemaking

engagement, the contextual triggers of sensemaking, the interpretive understanding of leadership transition, and the emerging constructs from the dual-lens analyses. Faculty, rank-and-file employees, students, and external stakeholders were excluded since the focus were for those occupying the mid-level official designations.

The study used a convergent parallel mixed-methods design (Cresswell, 2014), combining quantitative and qualitative data collected by a single instrument. A survey questionnaire was used to capture the sensemaking engagement; while, open-ended questions embedded in the survey questionnaire, generated the interpretive insights from the narrative statements of the participants.

The study had the following limitations: First, the written qualitative responses may lack the spontaneity and depth that could be extracted in a face-to-face interview data. Second, because of their positional roles, the views of the participants may had been influenced by their designations and relational sensitivities which may compromised honesty and diversity of viewpoints.

Despite these limitations, the study still provided a unique view about organizational sensemaking and advances understanding of leadership transitions in higher education by using a dual-lens, context-sensitive framework.

Definition of Terminologies

Sensemaking. This is the process where middle managers interpret and construct meaning from their experiences during leadership transition.

Dual Lens. These refer to the frameworks used in exploring how university middle managers interpret and respond during leadership transition. The frameworks integrate Sensemaking theory and Cynefin framework as one analytical tool.

Sensemaking Processes. In the study, this refers to the properties of sensemaking used which include identity construction, retrospection, enactment, social activity, ongoing process, extracted cues, and plausibility.

Leadership Transition. This refers to the change in leadership where the new head assumes the authority and responsibility from the previous head. The transition is usually marked by change in vision, policies, and organizational objectives.

Relational Trust. This refers to a condition where middle managers are perceived to be trusted by their peers; hence, their narrative framing is considered plausible.

Institutional Coherence. This refers to middle managers' ability to maintain stability and authority by maintaining alignment with the new leadership priorities and existing institutional values, practices, and commitment.

Adaptive Sensemaking. This refers to the adjustment made by middle managers while engaging in sensemaking such as repetitive engagement with cues, collaborative dialogue, and creating plausible narratives that enable them to manage ambiguity and sustain organizational resilience.

Recursive Process. This refers to the practices of middle managers in revisiting prior interpretations, testing them through action, and refining them through feedback and dialogue; thus, meaning-making is on-going.

Iterative Engagement. This refers to the repeated reflection, dialogue, and recalibration of strategies among middle managers.

Organizational (Institutional) Memory. This refers to middle managers' past experiences involving organizational changes used to stabilize current decisions, frame continuity, and evaluate new leadership directions.

University Middle Managers. This refers to the functional role of university officials and unit heads in facilitating communication between executive leadership and faculty/staff. These include Vice-Presidents, Directors, Deans, and Department Chairs tasked to execute and interpret policy at the university and unit levels.

Identity Construction. This refers to the process where middle managers adapt their identities with the ambiguous situation by engaging in retrospection.

Retrospection. This refers to middle managers recollection of related past experiences to inform interpretations and judgments.

Enactment. This refers to middle managers deliberate actions of engaging with institutional change through dialogue and collective formation of institutional narratives.

Social Activity. This refers to dialogic activities among middle managers that collectively generate meaning during transitions.

Ongoing Process. This refers to the continuous changes and reinterpretation of the leadership change narratives modifications by middle managers.

Extracted Cues. This refers to middle managers dependence on both official information (such as memos and policies) and informal cues (conversations and observations) to understand leadership transition.

Plausibility above Accuracy. This refers to information inclination of middle managers creating plausible and actionable narratives over factual accuracy.

Clear Domain. This refers to the situation where institutional norms and are used to interpret and manage leadership change.

Complicated Domain. This refers to the situation where expert consultation and specialized knowledge are sought to address leadership change.

Complex Domain. This refers to the situation where collaborations and adaptive strategies are used to address leadership change.

Chaotic Domain. This refers to situation requiring urgent, crisis-induced responses necessitating the quick restoration of order.

Disorder Domain. The refers to the situation where fragmented or challenged interpretations, occurring when middle managers lack consensus on which contextual domain applies.

Dialogic Collaboration. This refers to sensemaking process supported by conversations, feedback networks, and peer validation.

Situated Cueing. This refers to middle managers process of filtering cues based on credibility, urgency, and contextual relevance.

Strategic Plausibility. This refers to narratives about leadership transition which are considered credible and actionable.

Identity Resilience. This refers to middle managers strategy to maintain their professional identify amid uncertain condition through self-concept adaptation.

Adaptive Retrospection. This refers to middle managers assessment process of past experiences in making interpretation and decisions about leadership transition.

Leadership Transition. This refers to the change of leadership (Institutional head) in a Philippine state university which usually happens every after five years.

Collaborative Interpretation. This refers to the collective construction of meaning through dialogue and collective actions.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This section presents the literatures on organizational change and leadership transition. The review is presented in a thematic format starting with the theoretical concepts and assumptions of Karl Weick's *Sensemaking Theory* (1995) and Dave Snowden's *Cynefin Framework* (2007), *Context of Organization Change*, *Sensemaking During Organizational Change*, *Application of Sensemaking and Complexity in organizational Change*, *Convergence of Theoretical and Empirical Evidence*, *Sensemaking in Higher Education Amidst Transformation*, *University Officials as Sensemakers*, *Research Gaps in the Existing Literature*, and *Chapter Synthesis*. The review serves as the foundation of the study exploring how university middle managers make sense of institutional transformation.

Theoretical Foundations of Sensemaking

Understanding how people and organizations perceive and respond to change requires theoretical frameworks to explain the cognitive, social, and contextual processes constituting their meaning-making. The theory of Karl Weick (1995) offers a fundamental principle in explaining this especially on how individuals draw meaning from uncertain and ambiguous situations through construction of identity, retrospection, and extraction of cues. Weick (1995) said, "*How can I know what I think until I see what I say?*" briefly explains his concept of sensemaking where individuals tend to figure out what they think if they articulate it in words and make reflections.

In the *Social Psychology of Organizing* (1969/1979), Karl Weick (1995) initially articulated the idea that organizations are continuously interpreting ambiguous situations. This perspective was eventually expounded in his work "*Sensemaking in*

Organizations” (1995) where he argued that sensemaking is an ongoing retrospective development of plausibility where people usually reference their actions. Later refinements (Weick, Sutcliffe, & Obstfeld, 2005) introduced three key concept extensions: *sensemaking is a continuous process, it is inherently social, and it is firmly rooted in action*. These properties illustrate sensemaking as cognitive and performative rooted from interaction, collective actions, and the environment they collectively shaped.

Most organizational studies made use of sensemaking as a theoretical framework to understand how individuals in the organizations interpret and respond to ambiguous situations like transformation. Karl Weick (1995) proposed seven interconnected properties articulating the sensemaking process: *identity construction, retrospection, enactment of sensible environments, social activity, ongoing process, extracted cues, and plausibility over accuracy*. These properties operate in a loop to emphasize that meaning generation is dynamic and developing in nature.

Identity construction serves as the foundation of the process of sensemaking. Notably, people referenced and used their self-concept in apprehending events where the way they look at their self-alter their focus, prioritization of information, and framing of problem (Weick, 1995). This idea was positively endorsed by Czarniawska (1997) saying that identity serves as a cognitive and cultural reference to interpret change.

Retrospection has become central to sensemaking because meaning usually surfaces after-action. Integrated understanding is achieved among individuals by revisiting past experiences and combining them to create a significant narrative (Weick, 1995). This retrospective interpretation allows individuals to validate their past experiences and correlate with the formed organizational narratives. Czarniawska

(1997) argued that this retrospective narrative is important in reestablishing the equilibrium after organizational change.

The concept of enactment differentiates Weick's theory that individuals in the organization are not just reacting to their environments in fact they form part of their formation. According to Weick (1995), individuals usually "*act their way into understanding*" where behavior influences the way they interpret change more than their understanding. The idea corroborates the assertions of Brown, Colville, and Pye (2015) who stressed that sensemaking is performative.

Social activity is equally valuable in the process of sensemaking where meaning creation is co-constructed and validated by means of interaction. Weick(1995) asserts that legitimacy of interpretations is established by continuous dialogues, collective narratives, and institutional discourses. Similarly, Maitlis and Christianson (2014) stressed the collaborative nature of sensemaking where individuals in the organizations usually work to align among themselves as they rely on shared understandings to achieve legitimacy.

The ongoing nature of sensemaking affirms that the process is continuous and only stabilizes when plausible information is accepted as legitimate; however, it is continuously updated when new information take shape and the situation changes (Weick, 1995). This recurring nature of sensemaking is considered to be the fundamental aspect of the existence of any organization.

Extracted cues constitute all forms of information from gestures, events, phrases that individuals considered to be significant from the flow of information. These pieces of information becomes basis for a more comprehensive interpretations. Gioia and Chittipeddi (1991) had this assertion that extracted cues serve as a

significant factor in assisting managers to frame changes that align with organizational members.

Plausibility is about preference towards actionable information rather than facts. It is the pragmatic aspect of sensemaking. During uncertain situations, people tend to prioritize interpretation which are logically feasible instead of those empirically accurate information. Weick (1995) affirmed this perspective arguing that credible narratives are valued more over absolute clarity. The creation of plausible narratives allows prompt coordination and decision (Brown, Colville, and Pye, 2015).

These seven properties are individual cognitive activities characterizing sensemaking. It offers a new way of understanding how individuals cognitively create meaning during uncertainty.

On the other hand, changes and deteriorating role structures prevent collective sensemaking. This is consistent with the 1949 Mann Gulch wildfire as re-examined by Weick (1995) where evolving events and weak leadership role resulted to bad outcomes. Other similar research, elaborated on these arguments where crises situations trigger conditions such as disrupted routines, emotional arousal, and challenged to authority which hinder the formation of shared meaning (Maitlis & Sonenshein, 2010). In this situations, individuals are cling to narrative that creates harmony between realistic feasibility and emotional relief.

Sensemaking research has been prompted by the fundamental need to understand the dynamics of decision-making processes, disaster response, and other context related uncertainties. The sensemaking perspective provided enhanced understanding of organizational transformation which goes beyond structural or procedural change to the interpretive processes that come along with change. Gioia and Chittipeddi (1991) articulated in their research that seniors leaders in strategic

transformation tend to do initial interpretation of the change situation prior to cascading the information to others influencing behavioral path to acceptance or resistance. Similarly, Balogun and Johnson (2004) expanded this perspective with middle managers where routine dialogues creates a mental templates of conformity or contradiction to the change narratives. In critical approaches sensemaking is caught in the middle of power interplay between institutional norms favoring specific narratives while the other is the opposite (Helms Mills, Thurlow, & Mills, 2010).

Understanding the Cynefin Framework

The Cynefin framework, developed by Dave Snowden (2002) during his time at IBM, is a decision-making paradigm conceptualized to purposely help executives assess varying levels of complexity within the organizations. The framework was fully developed in 2003 in collaboration with Kurtz which focuses on understanding the interactions between cause-and-effect in various contextual conditions prior to making a response. Cynefin asserts that understanding the context marks the initial step to a successful sensemaking contrasting with the conventional model which shows predictability (Snowden & Boone, 2007).

The Cynefin Framework provides a diagnostic tool allowing leaders to assess the situations and respond accordingly. This form of diagnostic instrument proves important for complex and evolving organizations like universities characterized by varying logics and values making traditional leadership models inadequate. The Cynefin Mini Book (Snowden and Stanbridge, 2021) contended that the creation of the framework aims to unravel concealed assumption to facilitate adaptive leadership by highlighting environmental conditions prior to making a response. The framework makes system classifications of domains: Clear, Complicated, Complex, Chaotic, and

Disorder, each of which requires varying sensemaking strategies (Snowden & Boone, 2007; Clear Impact Consulting Group, 2018).

The clear domain is defined by cause-and-effect connections. Resolutions in this contextual domain are associated with the operating procedures and best practices of the organization. Complicated domain relies on predictable relationship despite necessitating further research to determine appropriate solutions. This context is most common during academic planning, accreditation, and policy evaluation, where expertise is vital (Snowden et al., 2020). The complex domain is characterized by emergent and unpredictable organizational results. Leaders need to investigate, perceive, and react in order to surface patterns using safe-to-fail experiment (Snowden & Kurtz, 2003). This domain shows strategic alignment with leadership transitions and institutional transformation where sensemaking is found to be adaptative and iterative (West et al., 2022). Significant disruption deficient in identifiable patterns characterized Chaotic domain. In this case, leaders have to be decisive in stabilizing the system before making further interpretation. This context normally persists in situation like pandemics or leadership discontinuity where organizations are prompted to make temporary engagement within this domain (Snowden, 2021). Disorder domain is described by ambiguity to which of the four domains is applicable. Leaders would usually resort to personal tendencies that at times prove to be inappropriate for the condition. This highlights the idea of over-relying to customary interpretive processes without making accurate assessment (Clear Impact, 2018).

Making Sense of Complexity and Uncertainty. The strength of the Cynefin Framework has been associated with its ability to direct organizational leaders to engage with uncertainty. Cynefin helps facilitate unstructured thinking and adaptive

response strategies within Complex and Chaotic domains unlike those inflexible planning models (Snowden & Boone, 2007). Snowden and Stanbridge (2021) presented a conceptual strategy known as "dynamic steering" defined as a methodology where leaders use feedback loops in order to assess changes, results, and eventually modify methods as needed.

This type of flexible perspective has been used in public administration and emergency responses. Gerster and Pryke (2021) have clearly articulated how Cynefin improve project management collaboration using a common lexicon in understanding ambiguous situation. Similarly, West et al. (2022) used the Cynefin framework for emergency healthcare primarily to develop the rapidity and efficacy of how decision-making is arrived. These applications also support its applicability to higher education leadership transition where change usually happens in a politically contested environments.

Notably, the framework further point out the psychological difficulties involved with leadership in a complex environment. Many academic leaders gained success in the structural hierarchy because of their professional accomplishments in the Complicated domain (technical proficiency) but this could have drawbacks in their effectiveness in the Complex environments which requires experimental leadership approaches (Clear Impact, 2018).

Application to Leadership and Organizational Change. The Cynefin Framework has been popularly applied to leadership development initiatives, organizational learning, and policy development (Cairney & Geyer, 2017). In the technical leadership perspective, Snowden (2021) stress the importance of making decision based on the prevailing situational-context to reduce overdependence on established best practices.

Combining Cynefin framework with sensemaking theory, to understand organizational change, has brought intrigue among scholars. Brown, Colville, and Pye (2015) has long been advocating combining complexity frameworks with interpretive methodologies. They acknowledge the idea that individuals in the organization needs to evaluate the nature of ambiguity prior to making interpretive activities. An idea which puts Cynefin as the initial step to sensemaking.

Literature exemplified the importance of the framework especially in leadership transitions where changes in the institutional landscape are uncertain and unpredictable. The concept of “fail-safe probes” of Snowden (Kurtz & Snowden, 2003) aligned with the experimental and adaptive nature of universities requiring constant adjustments to organizational decisions given the evolving nature of their environments.

Context of Organizational Change

Change in the organization is usually defined by complexity, disruption, and uncertainty. These situations prompted organizational members to make sense of the uncertain events and make appropriate response. Weick (1995), argued that the process of sensemaking is practically evident among individuals who construct meaning out of an ambiguous context to maintain coherent comprehension of their actions, roles, and organizational goals. The transformation period is critical as it requires individuals to re-align their focus with the new expectations with the old routines, changing power dynamics, and interpretations of organizational directions. The study of Maitlis and Christianson (2014) put forward the findings that change management is not just procedural but also an interpretive process and reliant to

negotiation of meaning. In other words, change is not just about execution but an ongoing social activity and cognitive process.

Institutional Transformation in an Evolving Contexts. Institutional transformation is defined by system changes from the organizations basic structures, normative standards, and everyday routines. In higher education and public institutions, transformations are driven by external influences, political dynamics, technological development, and globalization (Christensen & Ebrahim, 2006). Contrasting technological development with institutional transformation, the later requires deep reassessment of institutional resources, identity, and cultural nuances. In fact, according to Kezar (2014) transformation in higher education can only be effective if both structural and cultural changes are emphasized to align governance, resource management, and institutional values. Changing environments and conflicting demands contributes to the transformation dilemma among stakeholders in terms of initiating the planned change. In these situations, transformation develop into non-linear and context dependent process prompting leaders to a collaborative development of new narratives (Greenwood, Hinings, & Whetten, 2014).

Leadership Transitions and Role Reconfiguration. In organizational development, the transition in leadership is crucial especially if it means changing strategic direction, organizational identity, and individual responsibilities. It is not an ordinary personnel turnover. It is symbolic and transformative in nature as it alters balance and customary routines of the organization (Balogun & Johnson, 2005). Most of the time, the coming of a new leader is viewed as a deviation from the previous practices and redefinitions of positional roles. Ibarra and Barbulescu's (2010) argued that changes in positions entails new work identity which could prompt work re-alignment and changing expectations. Uncertainty is prevalent among heads during

leadership change as they will be confronted with new directives (Floyd, 2012). The period of transition necessitate making sense in order to understand changing power dynamics and institutional directions. Changing roles during transitions causes uncertainty; thus requires continuous interpretation of evolving events to readily adapt to the new organizational context.

Sensemaking and Organizational Change

Weick (1995) emphasized that sensemaking is one of the strategies in managing ambiguity brought about by organizational changes. It is both an individual and collective processes. Sonenshein (2010) argued the proactive nature of sensemaking where individuals tend to interpret the change narrative and own it. This also proves that it is not solely a cognitive process but clearly a collective endeavor.

Bridging the communication line between the head of institutions and the employees are the middle managers. The study of Balogun and Johnson (2004) and that of Rouleau (2005) highlighted middle-level managers as sensemakers and sense givers in situation where ambiguity is experienced. Their interpretive role centers on understanding change and convert it into words. Further, middle managers engage in interpretive reconstruction of information where they understand organizational changes and manage their roles in the organization (Balogun, 2003).

Strategic communication requires good framing to be effective as sensemaking goes beyond interpretation of changing events. It involves the creation of believable narrative. The use of framing as an interpretive tool direct attention to the narrative that highlights change discussions (Cornelissen et al., 2014). Change is commonly presented as essential, can be attained, or is consistent with the institution's objectives. When positive framing is applied, employees tend to accept change and

reduce their resistance. The framing of organizational change works as a communicative tool to set understandable narrative. This makes storytelling an important element which connects sensemaking and sensegiving together to establish alignment and coherence during uncertainties.

Sensemaking is not entirely effective. In fact, studies presented factors affecting sensemaking particularly in complex change environment. One of its major complications is information overload, characterized by contradictory messages or those lacking with adequate context, affecting employees' understanding of change (Weick, Sutcliffe, & Obstfeld, 2005). Organizational fear is another element which prevents individuals from expressing themselves. Further, emotional reactions such as worry and doubt can also hinder one's cognition of change which could result in disjointed or ineffective interpretations. Sensemaking can also be altered by power dynamics and stringent hierarchies especially in cases where leaders make narratives without involving those in the lower hierarchy (Helms Mills et al., 2010).

Applications of Sensemaking and Complexity in Organizational Change

A notable increase in the use of sensemaking and complexity framework in organizational change has been recorded along the areas of education, healthcare, and public administration sectors. Empirical researches documented how leaders utilized sensemaking to manage uncertainty and ambiguity in times of reform or crisis situations.

Maitlis and Christianson (2014) study's on sensemaking episodes in a crisis situation explored the impact of interpretive acts on how people make decisions. Their research showed that dialogic approach was effective in terms of generating more effective responses especially in difficult contexts. Van der Sluis and Knies (2022) made

a study in education where they found out that that the absence of collective sensemaking breeds oppositional perspectives to change. The findings emphasized the importance of a collaboratively developed narratives about the reorganization.

Research using Cynefin framework has proven to have enhanced the understanding of the influence of complexity on institutional decision making. Gerster and Pryke (2021) studies project managers who adapted the Cynefin framework to improve response to evolving situations. Similarly, West, Ramsay, and Hesselink (2022) used the framework to examine pandemic response strategies in higher education institutions and found out that leaders use collaborative methods instead of command and control model.

Complementary Viewpoints on Complexity and Ambiguity. Integrating Karl Weick's Sensemaking Theory and Dave Snowden's Cynefin Framework exhibit complementary perspectives in understanding uncertainty and complexity. Weick (1995) analyses how individuals and groups manage ambiguous situation through retrospective sensemaking, social construction of meaning, and the preference for plausibility over exact truth. On the contrary, Snowden's Cynefin Framework is a diagnostic tool in identifying solution based on contextual complexity (Kurtz & Snowden, 2003). Weick focuses on meaning-making via narrative and identity, whereas Snowden on categorization and adaptive action informed by system features. Both models converge in their characterization of organizations as dynamic, non-linear, and context-sensitive. Maitlis and Christianson (2014) suggested that combining interpretive insights with that of situational diagnostics provides a more compelling analytical views of organization. Weick's sensemaking provides how individual understand uncertainties; while Snowden's Cynefin gives the required action inside specific contextual domain.

Empirical Researches Combining Sensemaking Theory and Cynefin Framework. Some scholar has started integrating sensemaking theory and Cynefin framework in doing empirical study of organizational change. Snowden and Boone (2007) have acknowledged the significance of Weick's concepts in revealing how individuals create plausible narratives during uncertainties. Dörfler and Stierand (2012) have investigated leadership sensemaking in hotel management. The findings revealed how managers transitioned from interpretive and diagnostic modes as a reaction to changing circumstances. Recently, West et al. (2022) applied Cynefin-sensemaking hybrid in healthcare emergency response systems where results showed that immediate and reflective process were significant in ambiguous situations. The studies showed that combining sensemaking and Cynefin framework is feasible and can provide deeper understanding on how people manage change and their responses amidst evolving environment.

Theoretical and Empirical Evidences

Empirical studies showed that integrating context-based and interpretive framework offers deeper understanding on how individuals engage in sensemaking as a response to ambiguity (Maitlis & Christianson, 2014; Kezar & Eckel, 2002). Identity formation, cue extraction, and plausibility were the most common sensemaking properties used in making decisions during uncertainty (Balogun & Johnson, 2004; Floyd & Fung, 2017). Meanwhile, contextual classifications were substantiated in crisis management researches involving educational institutions as the starting point of individual and collective sensemaking (Gerster & Pryke, 2021; West et al., 2022). Generated themes emphasized change is by nature interpretive and emergent. Thus, institutional leaders manage organizational change using

change narratives aligning with the transformation (Rouleau & Balogun, 2011). Moreover, safe-to-fail experiments have received validation in education where innovation is found to be iterative (Snowden & Boone, 2007). These findings mean that effective leadership transition is dependent on the creation of relevant narratives based on prevailing environmental conditions.

The combination of sensemaking and Cynefin framework strengthen its theoretical applications. Scholars argued that both frameworks are complementary as they give researchers new lens in looking at organizational change.

Sensemaking in Higher Education

The changing landscape of higher education institutions prompted researchers to further explore applicability of the sensemaking theory on how individuals comprehend, negotiate, and react to institutional transformation. The interpretive roles of middle managers have been regarded as valuable element to maintaining organizational alignment despite structural reforms. (Maitlis & Christianson, 2014). Recent studies showed how sensemaking determine the success or failure of a systemic reforms in higher education. Murray (2014), in a longitudinal case study of the unsuccessful Post-Secondary Education Commission (PSEC) reform in New Brunswick, examine the failed attempt of the government to reclassify of several universities as polytechnic institutes due to its failure to establish cohesive and credible narrative towards the concept of reclassification. Diverse stakeholders, such as teachers, students, and community leaders, negatively construed the classification which obstructed the development of a unified framework that could have validated the transition. The absence of a compelling coherent narrative corroborates Weick's (1995) theoretical concept of that plausibility is regarded more over accuracy to

facilitate a more effective sensemaking in uncertain situations. Academic and administrative leaders must understand that their roles are constantly evolving where conventional academic management is progressively integrated with administrative responsibilities, and involvement with external stakeholders (Middlehurst, 2008; Kezar & Eckel, 2004).

University Officials as Sensemakers. As sensemakers, university officials engage in re-evaluating their professional identities and institutional roles during organizational transformation. This substantiates Weick's (1995) assertion that identity is not fixed but is reconstructed through retrospection and interaction. Identity reconstruction comes with the rising expectations among leaders to function as credible source of information (Whitchurch, 2008). A study among senior administrators during mergers and policy reforms were found to have portrayed themselves as bearer of change to preserve their authority (Stensaker & Norgård, 2001; Bolden, Petrov, & Gosling, 2012). Archer (2008) further observes that mid-level leaders reconcile their identity by developing a manager-academic personas integrating collegial credibility with managerial stance. Identity construction is crucial in terms of getting traction for support. This is because followers tend to rely on how leaders present themselves as indicator for understanding organizational direction.

Sensemaking as an interpretive framework facilitates their transition from ambiguity to action. The study of Birnbaum's (1988) on loosely connected institutions shows how leaders turn to informal networks and symbolic actions to alter decision-making in the absence of formal authority. Recent studies conducted during the COVID-19 epidemic indicate that CEOs employed iterative framing discussions, similar to Weick's (1995) concept of a "ongoing process", to evaluate assumptions and modify strategies in real time (Kezar, 2021).

In order to execute higher education changes, leaders must balance authoritative directives and collaborative culture. Research shows that top-down initiatives only meet success when the system allows bottom-up meaning-making (Kezar & Eckel, 2002). Mid-level administrators usually act as intermediaries to convert strategic priorities into locally relevant frameworks (Floyd & Fung, 2017). Bolden et al. (2012) argued that the distributed leadership model significantly increases organizational commitment among organizational members as they align their identities with change initiatives. In contrast, implementation of change without sufficient sensegiving breeds opposition as they would feel culturally disconnected (Macfarlane et al, 2024).

Studies and Best Practices Among Global HEIs. Cases from international higher education institutions (HEIs) show how sensemaking alters the institutional reactions to change. Maitlis (2005) found that, in a study on curriculum reform at a UK institution, the extent of stakeholder engagement affected the emotional tone and coherence of organizational narratives.

In facilitating successful leadership transitions, effective communication is important. Instead of enforcing change, these leaders resort to dialogue where organizational members collaboratively interpret their responsibilities, beliefs, and visions concerning transition. This corroborates Weick's (1995) claim that leadership fundamentally involves facilitation of credible narratives that diminishes ambiguity.

Taylor, Machado, and Peterson (2008) also presented the importance of interpretive leadership where leaders show sensitivity to institutional culture, values, and identity narratives. Bryman (2007) stresses the value of trust and credibility as foundational characteristics for leaders to be regarded as authentic and committed to organizational goals.

Gaps in the Existing Literature

Although there is an increase in researches conducted on organizational sensemaking and complexity, there are still gaps to be filled especially for higher education in the Global South. Firstly, despite the complementarity of Weick's Sensemaking Theory (1995) and Snowden's Cynefin Framework (2007), there is no study conducted integrating both frameworks as a unified analytical model. Most studies address both independently without exploring the synergistic potential of both to surface context and deeply explain meaning-making processes. The absence of integration neglects the potential to establish a framework that can tackle both structural ambiguity and interpretative dynamics.

Secondly, actual studies utilizing these frameworks applied to higher education institutions in the Philippines or even in Southeast Asia are few. The prevailing literature, if there are, predominantly emphasizes policy compliance, institutional rankings, and access. Studies offer less interest toward how academic leaders and administrators interpret leadership transitions or systemic reforms. The application of sensemaking processes in a Western academic environment is far more likely different from the Philippines higher education institutional landscape due to their hierarchical structure, sociocultural and sociopolitical landscape.

Thirdly, middle managers are acknowledged as instrumental in enabling change in international literatures; however, their exact function in reshaping institutional identity, translating strategy, and exercising interpretive functions within higher education is underexplored in non-Western contexts (Floyd & Wooldridge, 2000; Rouleau, 2005). They function within organizational culture facilitating and limiting their leadership conduct, and yet, their sensemaking is underexplored in the context of institutional reform.

There are dearth's of researches exploring how power inequality, gender, and relational hierarchy shape positional credibility and sensemaking narratives. On gender, recent study by Magpayo et al (2022) showed that female leaders and marginalized individuals usually faces sensemaking challenges on emotional labor and double standards in terms of leadership legitimacy.

Synthesis

The examined literatures confirm the growing academic acknowledgment of sensemaking and complexity as fundamental frameworks for comprehending institutional transformation, especially in higher education. Karl Weick's (1995) sensemaking theory provided a theoretical perspective in understanding how individuals and organizations make meaning amidst organizational uncertainty. Moreover, Dave Snowden's Cynefin Framework (Snowden & Boone, 2007) also offered a unique classification of decision-making contexts as a diagnostic tool which can be applied in evolving and changing situations.

Research indicates that middle managers are considered as crucial in the contexts of sensemaking and sensegiving due to their functional role in the organization as mediating agents between the top management and the stakeholders. Their interpretive sense of leadership, which has the power to change narratives, has been regarded as valuable in legitimizing change initiatives.

Despite the expanding interests to integrate Weick's and Snowden's frameworks, considerable gap still persist, especially in studies along Southeast Asian settings and Philippine higher education institutions. Empirical investigation of how academic leaders comprehend and respond to complexity through a combined diagnostic-interpretive framework is sparse. Similarly, the distinctive functions and

sensemaking techniques of middle managers in Philippine higher education institutions are inadequately understood, particularly within hierarchical, centralized, and culturally varied governance frameworks.

This study fills these gaps through the integration of the Cynefin framework and Sensemaking theory. The approach presents a new perspective in looking at sensemaking applied to organizational change in higher education. This offers a unique blend of contextually relevant framework for examining leadership transition in Philippine higher education.

Chapter III

FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

This chapter presents the frameworks of this study. The research is anchored on the Sensemaking theory of Karl Weick (1995) and the Cynefin framework of Dave Snowden(2007). These frameworks provide the lens to examine how middle managers in a Philippine state university interpret and respond to leadership transition.

Analytical Framework

Figure 1:
The Dual-Lens Sensemaking in Leadership Transition

The framework *Dual-Lens Sensemaking in Leadership Transition* provides a theoretical paradigm in understanding sensemaking in higher education during institutional transformation. The paradigm integrates contextual conditions and

interpretive properties to comprehensively understand how middle managers engage in sensemaking during change situations.

The outermost layer defines the ontological foundation of the framework through contextual conditions. The contextual trigger of sensemaking during leadership change does not rest on the Clear domain or Complicated domain nor the Chaotic domain. The predominant domain comes with the context of Complexity usually characterized by evolving dialogue, uncertainty, and the absence of clear information. This finding shows that higher education institutions are basically adaptive systems where the transformation cannot be reduced to procedural or expert-driven frameworks. The situation is completely relational which continuously shape the foundations upon which individuals derive meaning.

The second layer captures the epistemological foundations where middle managers engage in negotiation with the uncertainty of leadership transition. Sensemaking goes beyond simple understanding because it is social and dialogic process of interpretation and action.

The theoretical contribution is situated on the third layer where emerging constructs are derived from the findings of the study. The presentation is a looping connection between contextual and interpretive analyses. The constructs extended the conceptual idea of adaptive sensemaking where uncertainty is transformed into a comprehensible situation.

The institutional outcomes are at the core of the framework. Middle managers use adaptive sensemaking by reframing and harmonizing narratives to establish trust and transform ambiguity into an opportunity. The outcomes are the recurring product of the sensemaking processes. The paradigm make the distinction by emphasizing its

recursive nature where activities are repeated and refined reshaping the contextual situations and interpretations of leadership transition.

This framework using lenses connects two perspectives – context and process. It addresses the gap in the literature showing that sensemaking cannot be understood by just interpretive enactment alone. It has to be connected with contextual uncertainty. In the uncertain and complex landscape of higher education leadership transitions, adaptative sensemaking is demanded such that middle managers establishes continuity and authority amidst ambiguity of institutional directions. Here, a conceptual model is being introduce as a framework to examine and understand institutional change and an integrated lens for directing leadership in an adaptive systems.

Theoretical Frameworks

The study is theoretically anchored on two frameworks – the Cynefin framework (Snowden & Boone, 2007) and Sensemaking Theory (Weick,1995).

The Cynefin Framework. The Cynefin framework was developed by David Snowden and further articulated with Mary Boone (2007). It designed as a decision-making model to help individuals and organizations sense the nature of the situation before they make decisions. The framework introduces five domains of decision-making: *Clear*, *Complicated*, *Complex*, *Chaotic*, and *Disorder*. Each domain corresponds to a specified cause-and-effect structure and thus requires distinct modes of leadership, interpretation, and response.

Complicated situations require expert analysis in order to discover patterns and solutions. Complex environments, however, are characterized by unpredictability and emergent outcomes, where patterns can only be perceived retrospectively. Chaotic

situations need immediate more so new actions in order to restore order. Finally, Disorder or in some literature called Aporetic represents the situations where things are unclear which domain should applies due to lack of information (Snowden & Boone, 2007; Snowden, 2010).

The framework serves relevant during leadership transition where university middle managers perceive the situations as organizational change is evolving. Apprehension of contextual conditions may help them make sense of change and develop appropriate responses to complexity as it presents

Sensemaking Theory. The theory was developed by Karl Weick (1995). According to Weick (1995) sensemaking is a process where individuals interpret ambiguous or uncertain situations which disrupt organizational equilibrium. The main goal is to create a plausible explanation of the uncertain situation allowing individuals to engage and make appropriate response to change. There are seven key properties of sensemaking as identified by Weick (1995) - *Identity construction, Retrospection, Enactive environments, Social activity, Ongoing process, Extracted cues, and Plausibility over accuracy.* Weick (1995) argued that people do not respond to the reality itself but to the reality they construct through these processes.

The integration of these two frameworks creates an in-depth understanding how sensemaking transpires during leadership transition. When combined, they allow mapping of the complexity of the situations and the interpretive processes individuals do when engaging with uncertainty. To put it simply, the Cynefin Framework provides the structure for identifying the domain in which these processes transpire; while, sensemaking theory highlights the cognitive and social processes of sensemaking (Maitlis & Christianson, 2014; Kurtz & Snowden, 2003).

Chapter IV

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the research design, methods, and procedures used in this study. It thematically presents the research design, researcher's reflexivity, ontological and epistemological orientations, purpose and analytical integration, sampling procedures, instrumentations, data collection procedures, data analysis procedures, validity and reliability, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study utilized Convergent Parallel Mixed-Methods Design as the research approach. According to Creswell (2015), the design entails simultaneous collection of quantitative and qualitative data. It is appropriate for research exploring structural and interpretive processes.

Researcher's Reflexivity

Reflexibility is required in qualitative and mixed-methods researches to establish positionality, values and experiences of the researchers (Berger, 2015; Finlay, 2002). As an insider in the institution under study, the researcher has first-hand familiarity and understanding of the institutional culture, administrative structures, and leadership direction which could influence how data is interpreted. In this case, reflexivity was adopted. Firstly, the researcher engaged in on-going self-reflection, developing interpretations, and possible biases. Secondly, triangulation was used by the researcher through the integration of quantitative data with open-ended questions to make sure data interpretation does not depend on one source only minimizing over

dependence on the researcher's insiders experiences. Thirdly, the participants narratives were treated as significant statements incorporated in the data analysis to make sure interpretations are based on their experiences instead of the viewpoint of the researcher.

In this study, reflexivity worked as a methodological and ethical standpoint emphasizing the researcher's duality of positions maintaining the transparency in the production of knowledge. Here, reflexivity is used as a valuable tool to preserved the credibility, trustworthiness, and rigor of the study (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

Ontological and Epistemological Orientations

The study approach is structurally built on two frameworks offering different perspectives ontologically and epistemologically.

Ontologically, the Cynefin framework (Snowden & Boone, 2007) presents the nature of reality categorizing it into five contextual domains (*clear, complicated, complex, chaotic, and disorder*). Each of these domains presents a unique context-based approach to decision-making. This makes the Cynefin framework a diagnostic tool in identifying the environment where uncertainty is experienced by the participants.

The sensemaking theory takes the epistemological orientation positioning the nature and means of acquiring knowledge. It presents the idea of how individuals make meaning in response to the ambiguous situations. The theory highlights the seven fundamental properties of sensemaking: *identity construction, retrospection, enactment, social engagement, ongoing processes, extracted cues, and plausibility over accuracy* (Weick, 1995; Weick, Sutcliffe, & Obstfeld, 2005).

Creswell (2015) argued that philosophical assumptions are significant in the interpretation of data.

Purpose and Analytical Integration

The survey instrument was conceptualized using the Cynefin framework as a guide allowing the categorization of middle managers experiences into contextual domains. Statistical analysis was used to analyze responses to categories to show the engagement trends in various transformation situations.

Sensemaking theory presented the narrative responses of the participants and were analyzed using thematic and narrative analyses. The analyses were again guided by Cynefin contextual domains and sensemaking properties.

Integrating the nature of reality (ontology) and the means of knowing the reality (epistemology) generated a multi-dimensional understanding about sensemaking during leadership transition. The combination of contextual assessment and meaning creation showed the nature of domain shifting and the manner by which it was perceived and interpreted by university middle managers.

Sampling Procedures

This study utilized the same respondents for both survey and qualitative inquiries to make sure data consistency and complementarity. Creswell (2025) argued that this method is common in research using convergent parallel mixed-methods design where qualitative data are substantiated by quantitative data adding strength to the validity and coherence of the findings.

Quantitative Component. The quantitative part of the research used purposive sampling technique. A group of 30 university middle managers were

identified whom were engaged in leadership transformation processes. They were chosen based on their positions in the institution. Out of the 30 middle managers invited, 26 responded to the questionnaire with a response rate of 86.7%, appropriate for statistical analysis within a small, defined group.

Qualitative Component. Data for the qualitative component of the research were gathered through open-ended questions integrated into the same survey instrument. The qualitative sample was the same sample population used in the quantitative component from the identical group of 26 participants who freely responded to the narrative data. The method highlights the voluntary response sampling methodology among the purposively selected group (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018). The simultaneous collection of qualitative and quantitative data was employed due to the limited time availability of the purposely selected population.

Instrumentations

The research utilized one survey tool which integrate quantitative and qualitative survey and open-ended questions adhering to the convergent parallel mixed methods framework to facilitate the simultaneous collection of both quantitative and qualitative data.

Quantitative Instrument. The survey instrument was designed based on the seven sensemaking properties (*Identity Construction, Retrospection, Enactive of Sensible Environments, Social Activity, Ongoing Process, Extracted Cues, and Plausibility Over Accuracy*). Each property was composed of statements assessed using 7-point Likert scale from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 7 (Strongly Agree). The scaling was adopted to enhance variability of responses and increase the reliability of the instrument.

The researcher made survey questionnaire was pilot tested before its full-scale deployment to allow any adjustment in the items for clarity, phrasing, and coherence.

Qualitative Instrument. The open-ended questions for qualitative inquiry was embedded in the same survey instrument. These questions were positioned after each set of Likert-scale statements asking participants to reflect on their experiences on leadership transition.

The open-ended questions were constructed based on the sensemaking properties and Cynefin framework. This approach aims to establish the conceptual basis in understanding how participants construct meaning, whereas the Cynefin framework served as a tool for classifying the characteristics of the situations in which these sensemaking processes transpired.

Data Collection Procedures

This part discussed the procedures used to gather both quantitative and qualitative data.

Quantitative Data. A survey questionnaire was used to gather the quantitative data through Google forms to make it more accessible and easy to distribute. The link to the questionnaire was sent to the identified middle managers (N=30) using an online messaging application.

Qualitative Data. Data for the qualitative open-ended questions were collected simultaneously using the same instrument as the survey questionnaire.

Data Analysis Procedures

The discussion below outlines the data analysis procedure involving two-phase data analysis procedure.

Quantitative Data. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the quantitative data. This was comprised of means scores, mode, and standard deviation. Central tendencies were measured using mean and mode. Standard deviation was used to measure the variability in the respondents responses in terms of consensus or difference.

Quantitative data analysis used spreadsheets and statistical measures appropriate for small sample sizes.

Qualitative Data. Two-stage data analyses were used to qualitative data. First, narrative analysis was utilized to categories participants responses according to contextual domains identified by the Cynefin framework. This approach provided the diagnosis of the environment participants perceived prior to sensemaking. Second, the narrative data then underwent reflexive thematic analysis guided by the sensemaking properties. The process involve the generation of initial codes and themes in alignment with the sensemaking dimensions of Karl Weick. This analytic process aimed at interpreting how middle managers understand leadership transition based on their experiences.

Data Integration

Following the convergent parallel mixed methods design, the quantitative and qualitative datasets were collected simultaneously but were analyzed separately. After the analyses both data were integrated for interpretation. The integration involve the process of cross-property interpretation and theorizing of the combined data to surface sensemaking properties in the higher education leadership transition.

Validity and Reliability

The trustworthiness and rigor of the study was ensured using various strategies.

Quantitative Validity and Reliability. Content and face validity were conducted during the development of the instrument. Survey items were guided by Weick's (1995) seven sensemaking properties. The items were statistically evaluated to make sure the structure, clarity, and theoretical consistency of the items in the survey questionnaire are reliable. Pilot testing was conducted to establish face validity among a group of university faculty who assessed the clarity and phrasing of the items.

Cronbach's alpha was calculated for each of the seven subscales to evaluate dependability where all subscales were above the criterion of 0.70, signifying robust internal consistency.

Qualitative Validity. The qualitative tool validity was established using two strategies: data audit and member check (Creswell, 2015). Data audit was conducted by an expert in qualitative data analysis to determine transparency and dependability of coding and themes.

On the other hand, member checking was used to verify the accuracy of the interpretations made.

Ethical Considerations

Given the sensitive nature of responses, particularly on institutional leadership and change, the study put into careful consideration the ethical research practices. The participants were brief that their responses on the open-ended questions might involve reflections or critiques that could affect relational dynamics in the institutions.

In this case, the researcher strictly observed confidentiality of all responses. During transcription and analysis, participants were anonymized using codes to keep their identity confidential.

No participants were coerced during the conduct of the study. The questionnaire allow participants to skip items or questions they feel uncomfortable with especially in the open-ended questions. Compliance to institutional ethical standards were observed in the study and ensured that data were collected, stored, and reported observing the highest degree of integrity.

Chapter V

DIMENSIONS OF SENSEMAKING IN LEADERSHIP TRANSITION

This section presents the quantitative dimension of sensemaking in leadership transition measuring sensemaking engagements using descriptive statistics – mean, mode, and standard deviation.

Building Self-Concept in Uncertainty

Identity is the core of sensemaking as it is used to measure and assess engagement to change. In the case of university middle managers, their role as sensegivers – where they often cascade and renegotiate directives and information – continuously reshape their professional identity to adapt to the evolving condition be it minor or major organizational changes.

Extent of Engagement in Identity Construction. The table below highlights university middle managers' perception and understanding of their professional identity within the context of leadership transition.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics and Variability of Participants' Responses on Identity Construction

Statement	Mean (M)	Mode (Mo)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation (Mean)	Variability (SD)
1. I understand how my role contributes to the institution's transformation.	6.27	7.00	1.48	High	Moderate
2. The transformation aligns with my professional values and identity.	5.90	7.00	1.35	High	Moderate
3. I see my work as an integral part of the overall transformation process.	6.30	7.00	1.34	High	Moderate
4. The goals of the transformation are consistent with my	5.84	7.00	1.38	High	Moderate

Legend: Mean (M) Scores: >5.00-high agreement; 3.00–4.99 - moderate agreement; <3.00-low agreement. Mode (Mo): = 7.00- strong dominant agreement; Mo = 6.00-dominant agreement; Mo = 5.00-moderate agreement; Mo ≤ 4.00-weak/divided stance. Standard Deviation (SD): < 1.00-low, 1.00–1.49 - moderate, and ≥ 1.50- high.

The results showed high agreement (M>5.00) in all four statements which means that middle managers see their professional roles as important to leadership transition. This is supported by mode values indicating strong agreement (Mo=7.00) in all four statements which suggests that there was a strong common understanding among middle managers.

“I see my work as an integral part of the overall transformation process” received the highest scores in terms of Mean (M=6.30), Mode (Mo=7.00), and Standard Deviation (SD=1.34). This shows strong collective stance where they perceive their jobs as important to institutional change.

The statement, *“The goals of the transformation are consistent with my personal career objectives”*, received the lowest scores (M=5.84). Despite the lowest ranking scores, it still reflects a significant level of conformity (Mo=7.00) among respondents. Although, it can be noted that a minor tensions between personal goals and institutional objectives existed. From the insider view of the researcher, *Akeanon* concept of *“kato anay”* (way before) reflects respondents hesitation and opposition to change. Further, pragmatic compliance is also echoed in phrases like *“bisan sin-o eang masunod kita”* (whomever leads, we will just follow) and *“bahala eon galing”* (come what may). These highlight the interplay of resistance and pragmatism among middle managers.

The results of the standard deviation (SD=1.34 and SD=1.48) exhibit a moderate difference the respondents perspective. Despite strong agreement their point of views are moderately diverse. Variability may have been triggered by

respondent's differences in positions, responsibilities , and over-all perception of the new leadership.

These findings indicate that professional identity is used as a stabilizer to maintain alignment during institutional transition. The high means and strong modes stressed that majority of the middle managers understand that their roles were in alignment with the institutional transition. However, the noted difference in the mean and mode scores revealed the hidden conflict when personal goals are not in alignment with the objectives of the institutional change. This put forward the importance of communicating and structuring institutional reform initiatives in a manner that reinforces collective identity while facilitating individual professional development.

Reflective Meaning Creation

Retrospection is a process where event is interpreted based on prior experiences. In leadership change, retrospection aid middle managers to make sense of uncertainty by reflecting from past reforms or other similar events. This cognitive activity reinforces their professional identities and make decisions through an established reference points.

Extent of Engagement in Retrospection. Table 2 shows the results on how the respondents perceived the influence of prior experiences to their understanding of leadership change.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics and Variability of Participants' Responses on Retrospection

Statement	Mean (M)	Mode (Mo)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation (Mean)	Variability (SD)
1. I frequently refer to past experiences to guide our current decisions.	5.88	7.00	1.28	High	Moderate

2. Historical events in our institution influence how I perceive the transformation.	5.69	6.00	1.19	High	Moderate
3. Lessons I learned from previous changes are applied to the current transformation.	5.81	6.00	1.29	High	Moderate
4. I use historical successes and failures to shape our current strategies.	5.92	6.00	1.35	High	Moderate

Legend: Mean (M) Scores: >5.00-high agreement; 3.00–4.99 - moderate agreement; <3.00-low agreement. Mode (Mo): = 7.00- strong dominant agreement; Mo = 6.00-dominant agreement; Mo = 5.00-moderate agreement; Mo ≤ 4.00-weak/divided stance. Standard Deviation (SD): < 1.00-low, 1.00–1.49 - moderate, and ≥ 1.50- high.

The results above indicate that respondents were inclined to use their prior experiences in managing uncertainty during leadership transition. All statements were rated with high mean scores (M>5.00), while modes were concentrated at 6.00 or 7:00. This means that there was a general agreement and significant preference towards past experiences in understanding institutional change.

The statement, *“I use historical successes and failures to shape out current strategies”* received the highest mean score (M=5.92), mode at 6.00, and standard deviation at 1.35. The result expressed strong agreement among the respondents. There was a collective reliance on the so called institutional memory to guide decisions and actions.

Rated with the lowest mean score was the statement, *“Historical events in our institution influence how I perceive the transformation”* (M=5.69) despite receiving moderate scores in mode (Mo=6.00) and standard deviation (SD=1.19). The difference suggests that despite majority of the respondents value historical events, there were differences in the degree of reliance on past experiences.

The moderate difference in the response (SD=1.19-1.35) suggests that despite everyone was engage in retrospection intensity of engagement was varied. The variability may have been triggered by the respondents tenure and positional rank.

Middle managers with longer tenure and higher administrative roles have gained extensive institutional experiences which may have resulted to the observed variability.

As an insider, I have observed that long-serving middle managers always referenced to past memory when confronted with institutional change. Expressions like “*kami ta anay kato*” (before, this what we are..) and “*makara ta kami kato*” (this is what we are before) were evidenced of their reliance to their previous institutional experiences. These affects how middle managers perceive change. Instead of looking at institutional change as an opportunity, they are usually adamant changing those established practices with new directional approaches.

Mean and mode scores indicate that respondents used institutional memory and personal experiences to make appropriate response to uncertainty. This institutional practices strengthen continuity and stability; however, it can also prompt conservative decision-making stressing the dual role of retrospection as a resource and as a potential limitation to institutional change.

Constructing a Sensible Environment

Developing a sensible environment emphasizes that individual continuously shape and respond to uncertainty through ongoing interaction. This means that social environment is not predetermined or fixed rather it is made sensible by individual actions, interpretations, and decisions both cognitive and experiential.

Extent of Engagement in Enacting a Sensible Environments. Table 3 presents university middle managers’ engagement in shaping sensible environment during the leadership transition.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics and Variability of Participants' Responses on Enactive of Sensible Environments

Statement	Mean (M)	Mode (Mo)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation (Mean)	Variability (SD)
1. My actions during this transformation shape the outcomes we experience.	6.15	7.00	1.29	High	Moderate
2. I adapt my strategies based on feedback from our environment.	6.11	6.00	1.14	High	Moderate
3. The steps I take influence how the transformation unfolds.	5.96	6.00	1.08	High	Moderate
4. I proactively create conditions that supports the transformation process.	6.00	6.00	1.06	High	Moderate

Legend: Mean (M) Scores: >5.00-high agreement; 3.00–4.99 - moderate agreement; <3.00-low agreement. Mode (Mo): = 7.00- strong dominant agreement; Mo = 6.00-dominant agreement; Mo = 5.00-moderate agreement; Mo ≤ 4.00-weak/divided stance. Standard Deviation (SD): < 1.00-low, 1.00–1.49 - moderate, and ≥ 1.50- high.

The results showed high engagement among the respondents in shaping the transitional environment using their actions and decisions. The statement, “*My actions during this transformation shape the outcomes we experience*”, was the highly rated statement by the respondents (M=6.15, Mo=7.00, SD=1.29). This means that majority of the respondents recognized the impact of their actions towards leadership transition and eventually shape the outcome of the transformation.

On the other hand, the statement “*I modify my strategies according to feedback from our environment*” (M=6.11, Mo=6.00, SD=1.14) showed that respondents acknowledged the difference between feedback and their adaptative response toward the transition. However, the consistent scores for mean and mode signify that adaptability to change was innate among middle managers.

The statement, “*The steps I take influence how the transformation unfolds*”, received the lowest rating in terms of mean score (M=5.96) but was moderate in mode (Mo=6.00) and standard deviation (SD=1.08). This suggests that majority of the

respondents were taking actions towards creating a supportive environment for the transition. The tight scores between mean and mode clearly demonstrate that their proactive orientation is a widely shared position.

The moderate variability (SD=1.06-1.129) suggest difference in the respondents influence towards the creation of a sensible environment during the transition. The divergence is associated with the degree and extent of influence to initiate interaction and prevailing narratives. From the insider's point view, observation showed that long-serving middle managers usually exert more influence to others in shaping organizational outcomes. This can be observed especially during university wide meetings. However, new appointees typically adopt a more cautious and observant roles.

The results showed that creating a sensible situation during leadership transition was interpretive and performative. Respondents do not just simply make an understanding of the change narratives; instead, they also actively shape them with their actions, decisions, and plans.

Dynamic and Participatory Sensemaking

Social interaction facilitates sensemaking among individuals. This happens when there is a collective understanding to initiate an interaction due to the uncertainty. As a social phenomenon, this unfolds in dialogue, cooperation, and collective action.

Extent of Engagement in Social Activity. The table below presents respondents engagement with social activity in sensemaking during leadership change.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics and Variability of Participants' Responses on Social Activity

Statement	Mean (M)	Mode (Mo)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation (Mean)	Variability (SD)
1. Communication among colleagues is crucial in understanding the transformation.	6.53	7.00	1.03	High	Moderate
2. I often discuss the transformation process with my peers to make sense of it.	6.23	7.00	1.14	High	Moderate
3. Team meetings are essential for interpreting the changes we are experiencing.	6.15	7.00	1.40	High	Moderate
4. Collaboration with others helps me understand the broader impact of the transformation.	6.38	7.00	1.10	High	Moderate

Legend: Mean (M) Scores: >5.00-high agreement; 3.00–4.99 - moderate agreement; <3.00-low agreement. Mode (Mo): = 7.00- strong dominant agreement; Mo = 6.00-dominant agreement; Mo = 5.00-moderate agreement; Mo ≤ 4.00-weak/divided stance. Standard Deviation (SD): < 1.00-low, 1.00–1.49 - moderate, and ≥ 1.50- high.

The statement, “*Communication among colleague is crucial in understanding the transformation*” was rated high agreement among other statements (M=6.53), strong dominant agreement (Mo=7.00), and moderate difference in respondents perspective (SD=1.03). These results indicate that majority of the respondents saw peer communication as important during transition where ambiguity occur.

“*Team meetings are essential for interpreting the changes we are experiencing*”, received the lowest mean score (M=6.15), with strong dominant agreement (Mo=7.00), and increased variability (SD=1.40) in relation to other statements. The disparity between the mean score and mode suggests that despite majority of the respondents agreed, others expressed lower levels of agreement due differences in departmental communicative practices, leadership accessibility, and personal involvement within a collaborative environment.

Respondents had regarded social interaction as key to making sense during leadership transition. The combination of high mean scores and strong mode values across all statements indicated collaborative dialogue was important in understanding institutional change. Variability, although moderate, highlighted that respondents widely valued social interaction.

The moderate differences indicated that although social interaction is widely valued collaborative opportunities vary affecting participations in the construction of meaning about the context of ambiguity.

Making Sense Continuously

Sensemaking is a recurring process. It is influenced by ongoing encounters with changing contexts. As situations changes, individuals modify their interpretations based on new developments and contextual cues; thus, it is an ongoing process. However, this process is dependent on extracted cues, frequently ambiguous indicators, that facilitate interpretations.

Extent of Engagement through Ongoing Process. Table 5 presents the descriptive data about the extent to which respondents perceive sensemaking as an ongoing process during leadership transition. All four statements received high mean scores, between 6.30 and 6.42, with mode consistently at 7.00, indicating strong and dominant agreement.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics and Variability of Participants' Responses on Ongoing Process

Statement	Mean (M)	Mode (Mo)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation (Mean)	Variability (SD)
1. Sensemaking about the transformation is a continuous process for me.	6.42	7.00	1.03	High	Moderate
2. I regularly update my understanding of the	6.30	7.00	0.93	High	Low

transformation as new information emerges.					
3. My interpretation of the transformation evolves over time.	6.35	7.00	1.01	High	Moderate
4. Continuous reflection is important for making sense of the changes.	6.42	7.00	1.06	High	Moderate

Legend: Mean (M) Scores: >5.00-high agreement; 3.00–4.99 - moderate agreement; <3.00-low agreement. Mode (Mo): = 7.00- strong dominant agreement; Mo = 6.00-dominant agreement; Mo = 5.00-moderate agreement; Mo ≤ 4.00-weak/divided stance. Standard Deviation (SD): < 1.00-low, 1.00–1.49 - moderate, and ≥ 1.50- high.

High agreements were observed in statement, “*Sensemaking about the transformation is a continuous process for me*” (M=6.42, Mo=7.00, SD=1.03) along with the statement, “*Continuous reflection is important for making sense of the changes*” (M = 6.42, Mo = 7.00, SD = 1.06). These results mean that respondents were in collective agreement that sensemaking was an ongoing activity requiring continuous reflection to understand the context of leadership transition.

The statement, “*I regularly update my understanding of the transformation as new information emerges*” (M=6.30, Mo=7.00, SD=0.93) significantly had the lowest standard deviation among four statements. Low variability simply means that respondents had the highest degree of uniformity in their perception of the statement. The dominant mode across all four statements (Mo=7.00) suggests that majority of the respondents had strong agreement on the idea that they need to reassessed their interpretation of the transition as soon as new information arises. On the other hand, the statement, “*My interpretation of the transformation evolves over time*” (M = 6.35, Mo = 7.00, SD = 1.01) demonstrated significantly strong agreement that sensemaking was dynamic and evolves continuously to changing situations.

These results highlighted respondents understanding of sensemaking as a continuous and dynamic processes. High mean scores and dominant mode values strongly suggest shared understandings of leadership transition.

Interpreting Change Using Signs

Cues are incomplete and context-dependent signs. In an environment where situations and information are uncertain, these cues function as an alternative to factual information to create an initial understanding of the ambiguous environment.

Extent of Engagement through Extracted Cues. Table 6 highlights the respondents engagement in terms of extracting cues during leadership transition.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics and Variability of Participants' Responses on Extracted Cues

Statement	Mean (M)	Mode (Mo)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation (Mean)	Variability (SD)
1. Certain events during the transformation stand out as particularly significant.	5.46	6.00	1.55	High	High
2. I pay close attention to specific pieces of information to understand the transformation.	6.30	7.00	1.01	High	Moderate
3. Key moments in the transformation process shape my overall understanding.	5.46	6.00	1.67	High	High
4. I use critical incidents to make sense of the broader changes.	4.69	6.00	1.61	Moderate	High

Legend: Mean (M) Scores: >5.00-high agreement; 3.00–4.99 - moderate agreement; <3.00-low agreement. Mode (Mo): = 7.00- strong dominant agreement; Mo = 6.00-dominant agreement; Mo = 5.00-moderate agreement; Mo ≤ 4.00-weak/divided stance. Standard Deviation (SD): < 1.00-low, 1.00–1.49 - moderate, and ≥ 1.50- high.

Among the four statements, the statement, *“I pay close attention to specific pieces of information to understand the transformation”* received the highest mean score agreement (M=6.30, Mo=7.00, SD=1.01). These scores demonstrated strong and consistent conformity among respondents that selective attention on explicit information was important when interpreting institutional change. This means that respondents consistently rely on specific information prior to making interpretation.

The statement, *“I use critical incidents to make sense of the broader changes”* had the lowest mean score (M = 4.69). It can be noted that despite that majority

expressed agreement to this statement (Mo=6.00), a number of respondents scored it low causing the reduced mean scores. The variability across statements (SD=1.55-1.67) corroborated this result. These differences may have been caused by unequal access to information, and relational-closeness to those holding key cues about the transition. From my insider's observation, there exists selective information sharing available only among members of the trust-based networks affecting how cues are accessed and interpreted.

The results further indicated that respondents relied on environmental cues to understand the transition. This reliance, however, was dependent on cue availability as unequal sharing of information prevented continuous interpretation. The concept of the trust-based networks influence who will have the information and who will not.

Prioritizing Coherent Narratives

Plausible narratives are immediate and actionable, the reason why individuals prefer plausible information instead of waiting for what is accurate. In an evolving environment, such as an academic institution, actionable information are preferred for immediate decision-making.

Extent of Engagement through Plausibility Over Accuracy. Table 7 shows the respondents level of engagement on acting over plausible narratives during leadership transition.

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics and Variability of Participants' Responses on Plausibility over Accuracy

Statement	Mean (M)	Mode (Mo)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation (Mean)	Variability (SD)
1. It is more important to create a coherent narrative about the transformation than to have all the facts.	6.27	6.00	1.48	High	Moderate

2. I prioritize making sense of the transformation in a way that is practical and actionable.	5.92	7.00	1.35	High	Moderate
3. Developing a plausible understanding is more important than striving for complete accuracy.	6.30	6.00	1.34	High	Moderate
4. I focus on creating a story that makes sense, even if all details are not fully accurate.	5.85	6.00	1.38	High	Moderate

Legend: Mean (M) Scores: >5.00-high agreement; 3.00–4.99 - moderate agreement; <3.00-low agreement. Mode (Mo): = 7.00- strong dominant agreement; Mo = 6.00-dominant agreement; Mo = 5.00-moderate agreement; Mo ≤ 4.00-weak/divided stance. Standard Deviation (SD): < 1.00-low, 1.00–1.49 - moderate, and ≥ 1.50- high.

The statement, *“Developing a plausible understanding is more important than striving for complete accuracy”* received the highest mean score (M=6.30) from the respondents. This result suggests that most respondents preferred believability as criteria in interpreting the transition. The mode score supported this result (Mo=6.00) showing dominant agreement among the respondents. Further, the statement, *“It is more important to create a coherent narrative about the transformation than to have all the facts”* was also rated high (M=6.27) supporting the idea that actionable narratives were mostly prioritized.

“I prioritize making sense of the transformation in a way that is practical and actionable” (M = 5.92, Mo = 7.00, SD = 1.35) was rated low. Despite the low mean, the mode suggested strong dominant agreement. This highlighted strong preference towards practical and actionable strategies to facilitate immediate action and decision-making.

The moderate differences (SD=1.34-1.48) in the responses of the respondents significantly suggest that despite majority preferred plausible narratives, a few remain skeptical accepting them over data-driven or evidence-based information. These differences may be due to respondents cognitive strategies, experiences or roles.

From my insider's perspective, it is observed that respondents with longer experiences and close-ties with the leadership advocate trust-based explanations to maintain credibility and confidence. In other words, they only believe those whom they put their trust with. By contrast, young and less experienced respondents exercised caution by refraining from making interpretations without substantial evidences. Culturally, the words of senior officials possesses more legitimacy than those junior middle managers.

These results confirm that plausibility-driven sensemaking was the preferred interpretive strategy of the respondents during leadership transitions. The relatively high means and strong mode values suggested that majority of the respondents were for credible, cohesive, and actionable narratives.

Chapter VI

DYNAMICS OF SENSEMAKING

This chapter presents the qualitative analysis of the study using narrative and thematic analyses guided by the Cynefin framework and Sensemaking theory. The discussion is divided into two: narrative statements tracing how contexts influenced the conditions of sensemaking, and property-based interpretations that explains the participants understanding of leadership transition.

Conditions Prompting Sensemaking

Sensemaking is generally prompted by ambiguity or equivocality due to altered state of equilibrium; however, it is not known what specific context triggers it. This study assumed that ambiguity resides within a specific context which triggers the act of making sense.

This presentation analyzes the participants statements according to contextual domains to establish the situational triggers that encourages sensemaking.

Collaborative Adaptation in the Complex Domain. During leadership transition, it was found that identify construction occurred within the Complex domain characterized by uncertainty and emergent interactions. Here, identity was constantly shaped through collaboration among colleagues. According to some participants,

Even though things are uncertain I act with purpose and keep my mind on the organizations goals. (P2)

If things aren't clear I just thought about how I could help the university. (P12)

I see myself working with my coworkers and responding to the change to make sure our actions matter. (P13)

These statements from the participants imply that identity in the Complex domain was influenced by personal commitment to the institution and cooperation with colleagues.

Other participants developed a more adaptive form of professional identity where they first start with the Clear domain, characterized by distinctly defined responsibilities, prior to shifting to Complex domain. This shift happened as uncertainty increased. Several participants noted that,

When things are unclear, I adapt by focusing on working together and making contribution. (P1)

I adapt to stay in line with change, no matter if the situations is fixed or changing. (P9)

Some of the participants started with the Complicated domain, characterized by expertise and technical know-how, but shifts into Complex domain when expertise and technical reasoning do not work. Participants echoes their views,

I interact with a structured environment like ASU on purpose, but I change my behavior in situations that aren't clear. (P5)

In situations where I don't know what will happen, I rely on what I know and reshape my identity by working with others. (P8)

Although professional identity was based on knowledge and technical reasoning, these proved inadequate prompting participants to redefine their identity to develop an adaptive approach when uncertainty increases.

There were participants who started with the Chaotic domain, usually characterized by fragmented information, where identity depended on personal values but found it difficult to blend with uncertainty. Two participants acknowledge this,

Some parts of the change don't fit with my personal values or career goals. (P4)

As the institution advances, I remain resolute in my personal principles and uniqueness. (P6)

The Complex domain highlights the importance of identity to counter increasing uncertainty. It was noted that participants achieved a stable sense of identity in a complex environment where they co-construct meaning through collaborative activities. The participants professional identify in this type of environment became dialogic and relational rather than self-defined.

Alignment through Domain Shifts. Retrospection was found to had mostly occurred in the Complex domain. An environment where past experiences and institutional memory were used to understand the transition. This process helped participants maintain alignment with the incoming administrative leadership. As such, retrospection became a dynamic tool for understanding the leadership transition. Participants had these views,

My past experiences give me a sense of purpose, strength, and flexibility that helps me through the change. (P2)

Every change makes me feel unsure, but I stay connected with the goal by remembering what I've been through before. (P11)

My experiences help me see through problems. (P19)

These standpoints from the participants illustrate Complex environment as the point of retrospection where recurring construction of professional identity happened to adapt with changes. However, some participants exhibited domain shift from unstable situation prior to stabilizing in the complex environment. Others even commenced with Clear domain. The following participants expressed their views on this note,

..even though the new VMGO fits well with my professional goals, I still used what I remember from the past to deal with the current changes. (P10)

Institutional continuity helps me understand the changes that are happening now. (P7)

My past experiences with innovation and development shape how I handle change now. (P8)

My past work on projects that focused on development gives me an idea to help me understand the new goals. (P14)

These assertions from the participants indicate that retrospection was used as a strategy to adapt when situation was uncertain. Although, some participants perceived the transition from the standpoint of Clear or Chaotic domains, they ultimately settle in the Complex domain where they can freely construct their own understanding of change. Retrospection was not just a mere recollection of prior experiences. These were reconstructed to develop an actionable narrative to understand the transition and align with the new leadership.

Co-Creation of Sensible Environments in Complex Contexts. The enactment of sensible environment happened within the Complex domain where relational and collaborative activities occurred. Institutional environment was actively developed through interaction and deliberate activities of making sense of the uncertainty of leadership transition. The enactment was not directed but an intentional action as participants worked to deliberately understand the changes they experienced. It was grounded on the collective construction of meaning to align with the change narratives and mentor others. Participants had these views,

I work hard to create a positive work environment that encourages change. (P1)

The things I do, especially the ones that help me grow as a person and teach others, help people become more resilient when things change. (P2)

Some participants commenced enactment within the Complicated domain. They perceived the transitional change as product of system planning. Technical expertise was used to commence action even affirmed that systematic approach was enough to understand change. For instance, these participants shared these insights,

I have an effect on outcomes by planning ahead, working together, and thinking ahead. (P6)

My actions as a leader have a direct effect on the climate on campus, but the most important part is how well all work together. (P9)

These statements illustrate that structured approaches may initially give stability to uncertain situations but were not enough to sustain the accelerating uncertainty. Participants eventually transitioned to Complex domain where relational overrides gave an actionable change narratives.

In some instances, participants' enactments were consistently situated within the Complex domain with no trace of shifts. Participants stressed relational dynamics impacting the way they see the transition,

My unit's work affects the morale of the whole institution, so I make sure that everyone is involved in a positive way. (P7)

I think that change is something that everyone on the team should work on together, and our environment shows that. (P11)

Enactment of a sensible environment may have been an individual cognitive activity; however as actions evolved within the complex domain, it became a social action dependent on dialogue and collaborative construction of meaning.

Co-constructing Meaning through Clear-to-Complex Shifts. Social activity expressed through dialogue and interaction were situated in the Complex domain. Participants viewpoints stressed the role of communication as the principal mechanism in understanding the uncertainty brought about by the transition. They also

emphasized that making sense was a collective activity and that dialogue served as an adaptive strategy in managing complex situations. Given that communication involves relational and emotional dynamics, trust-based collaborative activities were necessary. Several participants shared this view,

I gain insights that help me deal with change by talking to my coworkers. (P1)

Collaborative dialogue is an essential element in understanding institutional transformation. (P4)

During the transition, communication helps people trust each other, work together, and feel like they belong. (P7)

We learn more about the transformation by talking to each other and giving feedback. (P9)

These views suggest that social activity was an iterative process of re-interpretations as soon as new cues about the transition are available.

On the other hand, an indication of domain shift commencing from Clear domain to Complex while uncertainty increases. Dependence on rule-based exchanges eventually transitioned to collaborative negotiation if formal communications were inadequate. Others prioritize the importance of collective dialogue to explore multiple views. Participants reiterated these ideas,

I often rely on informal conversations to assess and improve my understanding especially when formal communication is not available. (P2)

I can see things in a new way and change how I do things when I hear different points of view. (P10)

Talking to other people helps me understand things better and feel better about what I'm doing. (P12)

These reflective statements from the participants showed that interactions was necessary to turn uncertainty into actionable information. Social activity helps people maintain flexibility; while, communication served as a tool for interpretive activity and

trust-building which typically happens within the Complex domain - a context conducive to collaboration.

Iterative Sensemaking Anchored in the Complex Domain. Ongoing process located its activities in the Complex domain. It was an acknowledgement that leadership transition was indeed a continuing process of re-interpretation and adaptation. Here, change was characterized as dynamic, emergent, and cyclical. Participants articulated these views,

I have learned that change is a process that has no ending. (P2)

I now see change as collection of past experiences that are always getting better with new lessons. (P3)

Making sense is an ongoing cycle that doesn't have a clear ending. (P4)

I see the leadership transition as a change that requires being able to adapt. (P5)

These statements point to the idea that ambiguity was a common situation in a normal state of organizational existence. And, communication had been regarded as the foundation that maintain the ongoing process of adaptation. Some participants had these views,

I deal with the complexity of university life by constantly interacting with others and getting feedback. (P6)

I take part in open conversations, get feedback, and use it to change what I do. (P8)

I see change as a process that is always changing and never ends. (P7)

I see the leadership transition as a process of constant learning with adaptation being the only thing that stays the same. (P9)

Other participants' stressed the pragmatic view of change as a progressive process of refinement and experimentation. Progress was emergent requiring

patience to achieve significant results. The following narratives from the participants illustrate these points,

I recognize that institutional information are rarely conclusive and are continuously improved. (P10)

I see the transition as a process of trying things out and learning from mistakes over time. (P11)

Contrasting these patterns with the previous discussion where participants shifts across domains, the ongoing process was consistently within the Complex domain.

Situated Interpretation in Complex Contexts. Narrative views of the participants revealed that cues were mainly situated in the Complex domain. According to them cues were indicators consisting of formal (memos and policies) and informal communications (conversations and observations) that acquired meaning through interactions among the participants. Formal communications were considered cues when these were situated within a wider social contexts. In fact, cues were often times described as multiple, complex, and interconnected to differentiate them from formal and routine engagements. Participants echoed these statements,

Getting ready for change is a sign. I observe how others are adapting. (P2)

The way leaders act and the choices they make about their decisions are signs of how the transition will go. (P5)

I use feedback from stakeholders, performance metrics, and informal cues to decide what to do. (P8)

I see the need for a complete and varied approach because no single cue can explain the change. (P9)

The knowledge and actions of the confidant of the new head in the university are my main clues. (P11)

The best signs I see are in how people work together and talk to each other. (P13)

These statements showed that cues were not just product of observation, but were made meaningful through interaction, practices, and the way institutions worked. There were Clear domain shifts reflected in the statements of the participants, where what looked like clear cues were recontextualized in the Complex domain. A number of participants proved these points,

At first, the new president's appointment criteria were a clear guide, but later I saw them as signs that priorities were shifting. (P7)

I look for signs in the gap between how well we are doing now and how well we want to do in the future. (P14)

The training sessions and the sharing of resources show what is really important during this change. (P15)

The best cues come from paying attention to how people talk to each other without saying anything. What people say and what they don't say. (P16)

The above statements emphasized the idea that cue extraction was about interpreting the beyond surface meaning of relational dynamics. The analysis stressed that cue extraction was predominantly contextual and interpretive. The dominance of Complex domain in the narrative statements of the participants showed that cue extraction was more of a situated cueing where information were sorted, reinterpreted, and put together for clarity guiding people to make actions.

Strategic Credibility Emerging in the Complex Domain. Plausibility is about identifying what is "good enough". Good enough is the actionable narrative which guides the action of making decision.

The analysis showed that making plausible actions were constantly located within the Complex domain. Participants regarded plausibility as functional interpretations facilitating sensible understanding of the ambiguity due to leadership transition. These interpretations becomes functional when socially validated through

dialogue. Further, it was cyclical because new information prompts recalibration of that functional interpretation. Participants articulated these,

I worked with my coworkers to compare our interpretations and see if our conclusions are correct. (P3)

Even if I don't have all the information, I try to find a balance between making reasonable speculations to move forward. (P5)

I'm still open to feedback and new ideas that will help me see things in a new way. (P9)

I make decision if the information I have is good enough to make a choice, even if it is not entirely accurate. (P10)

These views from the participants practically showed that plausibility was based on sufficiency and relational trust instead of complete accuracy. The balance between correctness and plausibility were also put into consideration for some participants.

These perspectives were echoed by the participants,

I depend on reliable and knowledgeable people in the institution to confirm that my conclusions are reasonable enough. (P12)

I think that both plausibility and accuracy are important, but during times uncertain times, plausibility enables us to take action immediately. (P13)

Participants put value over accurate information, but when immediate decisions and actions are required they tend to turn to functional and actionable interpretation. Shift in domain was evident among participants where they commenced within Complicated domain (prioritizes accuracy and data-driven reasoning) but move to Complex domain where they transitioned favoring plausibility as uncertainty heightened. Participants have these perspectives,

Data-driven decision-making is my main guide, but when speed and flexibility are more important, I use information that makes sense. (P1)

I base my understanding on data-informed decisions, but I move towards collaborative testing of what appears to be reasonable in the absence of clarity. (P2)

Among the participants, accuracy was the initial criterion in understanding the transition; however, when transitional uncertainty increased they resorted to immediate and flexible decision-making using plausible information. This observation confirms that plausibility is contextual, relational, and adaptable serving as the channel between uncertainty and action. In the Complex domain, plausibility emerged as a practical response to uncertainty; while accuracy, valued in a structured environments, was re-interpreted and became secondary in terms of responsiveness and relational validation.

The shift from Complicated to Complex domain highlighted the adaptive response of the participants to the evolving condition of the leadership transition. The shifting domains exemplify the repetitive nature of sensemaking. Stability was achieved when no new actionable information were available, but while uncertainty increases the process of modifying, evaluating, and validating information through collective dialogue continued.

Making Sense of Leadership Transition

This section discusses the participants understanding of leadership transition. The analysis elaborates how interpretations are made and change, showing how the properties of sensemaking and the process of interpretation work together.

Adaptive Self. The theme, *Identity as an Adaptive Self*, explains how the participants make their professional identity through collective engagement.

The theme was built by three sub-themes which include *Role and Institutional Alignment and Institutional, Enactment through Intention*, and *Relational Adaptation and Value-based Interpretation*.

Role and Institutional Alignment. This sub-theme shared that the participants professional identities were rooted in the institutional structure. In other words, their identities were based on their functional roles in the institution which gave them sense of alignment during periods of uncertainty. Others shared that their identities were shaped by affiliations. It becomes more defined when obligations were associated with recognized institutional requirements and positional authority. Several participants made these remarked,

My identity is based on supporting systems that keep institutions honest.
(P3)

I understand who I am by connecting it to the progress of institutions. Those strategic goals guide my actions, whether they are clear or not.
(P14)

When I associate my role to our strategic goals, it becomes clearer. (P2)

As the [redacted], I know that my job is to help in managing the institutional transition. (p17)

Some participants described their identify as defined by institutional expectations. This means that their identity was associated with their role-based expectations to deliver expected outcomes. A participant had this view,

I make sure my role fits with what is expected of me and use that to get things done. (P1)

The analysis shows that during change leadership, relationships and understanding of the transformation helped shape identity. It is evident that participants maintain the stability of their roles through an established processes, policies, and mandates. Further, to make their professional

identities remain credible, consistent, and relevant, participants make use of the institutional frameworks as their point of reference.

Enactment through Intention. Participants constructed their identities through intentional actions to contribute to and interact with both structured and ambiguous environments. Even though situations were unclear, their professional identities were still rooted to the goals of the institution and their commitment to serve. Participants articulated these,

Even when things are not clear, I stay focused on my job of helping faculty and students make meaningful changes. (P5)

When things are complicated or unclear, I focus on making long-term improvements. (P12)

When things are not unclear, I just try to figure out what I need to do. (P13)

My role is still to help students learn and provide them the best learning. (P15)

These statements clearly showed that uncertainty encouraged participants to articulate their identities through contribution and accountability. This forward-looking view was associated with the broader aspiration of the participants. A participant echoed this,

I see myself as a person who helps bring about change by connecting the university to the global academic community. (P20)

The analysis reveals that professional identities are manifested through deliberate intentional actions instead of their institutional roles. Participants showed that coherence of identity from their active choices to lead and innovate; thus, identities become performative and dynamic.

Relational Adaptation and Value-based Sensemaking. Participants stressed the formation of their professional identities based on the institutional frameworks, intentional actions, personal ideals, and relational commitments.

These identities stabilized when they gained power over uncertainty. The framing of these identities depended on how they see their roles. Others looked at it through the lens of leadership accountability and ethical positioning which they considered important. Several participants had these views,

When roles change or are not clear, I focus on giving faculty more power and getting students more involved. (P21)

...as the institution moves forward, I continue to hold on to my own beliefs and values. (P6)

I stay clear-headed by remembering my leadership duties, whether the situation is set in stone or changing. (P9)

...no matter what kind of change it is, I stay focused on communicating its value. (P19)

I interpret my role through ethical planning. (P23)

Based on the participants' privileged voices, their professional identities were dependent upon relationships and values. Trust-based communication helped stabilize these professional identities situated within the networks of collaboration and accountability. This meant that identities were collaboratively developed and were rooted in their personal ideals.

As an extension of these narrative voices, my insider's perspectives confirm that participants strongly depend on their core values as their guiding principles. Most of them have this conservative identity which favors old practices and is adamant to change. However, despite this conservatism, identities are still relational in nature and are value-based.

Adaptive Alignment. The theme *Retrospection as a Negotiated Reality* speaks of how prior experiences are used as a guide and a reflection of the new reality where institutional memories are used to align current understanding with long-held values, practices of resilience, and cautious actions to create the so-called negotiated

reality. Negotiated because the reality is formed using the application of past experiences to create a new understanding of the present uncertainty; hence, the new negotiated reality.

This theme was reinforced by two sub-themes extending its theoretical assumptions – *Strategic Clarity through Reflection*, and *Guarded Retrospection as Caution*.

Strategic Clarity through Reflection. Participants used retrospection as a framework to understand leadership transition. Past experiences served as a practical approach to clear uncertainty and make decisions. It was not simply a cognitive act of recalling similar experiences, but was a collective action converting these experiences to a more dynamic strategies. These views were echoed by the participants,

When things aren't clear, I use SWOT and past analysis to figure out both the risks and the chances. The past of an organization can serve as guide. (P11)

...my past experiences help me make better decisions when things change. I use what I've learned to do my job better and faster.(P3)

My previous role in leading academic reforms has reinforced my conviction regarding the necessity of a clear, collective vision. I use what I've learned to make sure that the goals of my department fit with the changes in the university. (P5)

My style of leadership is based on the university's historical past and the work that has been done in the past to help students grow and do well. When things get hard, I use methods and the results that have worked in the past. (P9)

My past experiences taught me how important it is to be clear and have a plan for the future. This experience helps me make sure that new changes fit with the bigger goals of the institution in general. (P13)

These statements suggested that retrospection was used as a reference point and a pragmatic approach to making decisions. Prior experiences were used as dynamic guide to create clarity, stability, and purpose during the

transition. Using institutional memory on their current decisions, they were able to strengthened the connection between previous reform experiences and the current change objectives. This allowed them to perceived the transformation as an opportunity instead of disruption from their established administrative routines.

Guarded Retrospection as Caution. Some participants found retrospection as a cautionary measure to manage uncertainty of leadership transition. Prior experiences on reform inconsistencies and failures cultivated mistrust from other participants making them adamant about the transitional leadership change. Past disappointments contributed to this cautionary approach. Some participants had these views,

..when change doesn't fil with what I've learned in the past or in my career, I might be more hesitant to accept it. (P4)

..even though the new VGMO is consistent with my professional values, I will keep an eye on how it develops. History has shown that good intentions don't always lead to action. (P10)

Othe participants highlighted the interplay of institutional expectations and their professional identity prompting them to assessed the alignment of their principles as against the transitional objectives and re-examine the significance of their previous practices. Most of the time they exercised caution as they become apprehensive from experiences that did not completely aligned with their principles.

The change makes me think about how my values fit with the goals of the organization and how I used to do things. I see it as a compromise between what the institution needs and who I am as an officer. (P24)

...because the change seems okay with my professional identify and values, I think about past efforts that also focused on shared goals. This consistency affects how I make decision today. (P26)

..but it shows caution because I've been in situations before that didn't fully math with y values. This makes it harder for me to associate with the current change. (P4)

The above narratives showed that retrospection was perceived as a protective filter where participants evaluated leadership transition with learned lessons from their past experiences. In other words, their experiences were set as cognitive and collective boundaries where clarity of uncertainty was attributed.

From my insider's observation, retrospection is extensively used by participants. Senior middle managers tend to challenge change initiatives though leveraging their vast experiences; while, younger middle managers typically depend on codified processes and formal structures as their interpretive framework. This generational gap exposes retrospection as political and adaptive where senior officials dominate narratives of continuity though institutional memory, whereas junior officials prefer procedural rules.

It can be deduced that the act of retrospection was a cognitive guide, a moral compass, and a protective shield allowing the participants to manage their understanding of leadership change while exercising an individualized cautionary views.

Situated Action. Participants ability to make deliberate actions during uncertain situations is forwarded by the theme "*Situated Intentional Action*".

Participants' actions are shaped by the context of leadership change, powers relations, and institutional rules. The reflexivity allows participants to reassess decisions, reinterpret cues, and recalibrate actions without abandoning their responsibilities as officials.

The theme is further elaborated by two sub-themes the *Enactments by Intentional Action*, and *Sustained Engagement*.

Enactments by Intentional Action. This sub-theme emphasized that the creation of a sensible environment during uncertain situations was deliberate, and purposively done by the participants. They were not just reacting to change rather they brought certain conditions collectively through their actions. The actions were intentional because they were deliberately chosen and that they were aware of any potential drawbacks of their actions. These were what the participants think about,

...contribute with purpose, no matter what the situation is clear or changing. I have influence with my proactive mindset. (P26)

The university's transformation agenda can be influenced by what I do, the likes of building partnerships with international academic institutions and making it easier for students to get exchange programs. (P20)

I help shape the results of change by leading by example and vision. The way I act, like encouraging new ideas and helping faculty grows, sets the tone for departmental involvement. (P5)

I plan, work together, and take care of IP well to shape how the change happens. (P8)

The way I lead has a direct effect on how the campus grows, such as better board exam results and job opportunities to graduates. (P9)

In order to understand leadership transition, participants had to purposely do it among themselves. Making intentional action, they deliberately produced their own understanding of uncertainty at hand. They then collectively validated this interpretation; hence, it was performative and generative.

Sustained Engagement. Participants emphasized that in order to manage uncertainty, they had to be resilient and consistent. They maintained engagement through plausible narratives which became the stabilizing response to uncertainty. The participants made these remarked,

My actions help make things more coherent. This helps everyone move in the same direction to keep moving forward. (P17)

I took action to stabilize and guide the change, whether they are planned or not. (P25)

My actions have led to changes that are easy to see and immediate. Even small contributions can help things move faster. (P24)

I help keep the university moving towards its bigger goals by taking actions that are focused on students and their goals. (P12)

Ethical commitment further solidified participants resilience towards the uncertainty they experienced. This showed how integrity strengthened individual determination and collective goals. This was supported by one participant,

I promote ethical fairness and trust in the institution by encouraging ethical behavior and reducing bias. (P15)

This shows that sustained engagement is back-up by participants valuing integrity and restraint. It actually entailed collective practice of resilience despite the fact that situational circumstances are not clear. Reliance with plausible narratives help them remained focus to the transitional goals without requiring absolute certainty.

Collaboration through Dialogue. In this dimension, participants view sensemaking as dialogic and collaborative. Its social nature advanced the theme *“Collaboration through Dialogue as Core of Sensemaking”* where meaning is constructed through collaborative dialogue. The theme is supported by the sub-themes *Communication as a Shared Activity*, *Dialogue as a Retrospective Process*, and *Professional Self as Outcome of Collaborative Dialogue*.

Communication as a Shared Activity. Peer to peer communication allowed coordination of interpretations about the ongoing change. It also

permitted the validation of these interpretations through dialogue. Dialogue was considered the core of this shared activity. Participants' statements had these insights,

Talking to my co-workers gives me different points of view that help me understand better. (P1)

...we talk to each other to help us all understand the change. (P15)

...these talks help people understand each other and tell them what to do. (P13)

...talking to our co-workers helps understand where the transition is going. (P6)

...communicating to co-workers is important in making, judging, doing tasks. (P23)

In order to achieve clarity, alignment, and organization amidst the ambiguity of transition, participants engaged in dialogue. It was where they developed their interpretations, validated their assumptions, and created shared understanding for coordinated actions. This allowed them to manage ambiguity by collecting insights, confirming various interpretations, and negotiating understanding until a collective meaning was formed.

Communication is a shared activity as participants intentionally come together to make dialogue. They have one common purpose to translate complexity into a coherent understanding such that everybody remains connected with the institutional directions.

Dialogue as a Retrospective Process. This sub-theme suggested that retrospection was not just an individual cognitive activity but also a collective activity. When engaged in dialogue, participants collectively used their past experiences to explain current uncertainties. Retrospective communication allowed them to adjust their approach and enhance their strategies in managing

the transition. They also emphasized the reflexive relationship between past and present experiences to generate actionable narratives about the transition.

The participants had these views,

I frequently depend on informal interaction to assess and enhance my comprehension. (P2)

...collaborative conversation is very important, especially when things are hard to understand. (P4)

I use ongoing conversations to connect my thoughts with past events to make sense of changes that are happening now. (P7)

...talking to each other help me connect old strategies with new reforms so that we don't make the same mistakes again. (P18)

...communication helps me think about what I'm doing and change it, whether things re clear or not. (P26)

Dialogue is not about exchanges of information. It evolves into a cyclical and retrospective processes where past experiences are used as part of the communicative exchanges to refine strategies, anticipate drawbacks, and make adaptive approach to the demands of the transition.

Professional Self as Outcome of Collaborative Dialogue. This sub-theme stressed that collaborative dialogue shaped the participants professional identity. According to the participants, it reinforced their professional values, clarified their institutional responsibilities and confirmed their professional roles in the transition. The more they engaged in interaction, they strengthened their resolve based on how they see themselves and their positions. This highlights the relational dimension of dialogue where it becomes a reflective space for assessing roles and identities.

I make sure that my actions are in line with the change by talking to people. (P11)

...communication build trust, teamwork, and responsibility when things are changing. (P7)

...having interaction with others helps me remember that I am someone who is committed to innovation and excellence. (P21)

Talking to my coworkers helps me figure out who I am in the organization. (P19)

...dialogue gives me the chance to rebuild my professional identity as things change. (P24)

Professional identity was not fixed. It was co-constructed when one engaged in a collaborative dialogue. It served as a reflection of the participants commitments where it reshaped their identities as a response to the evolving expectations of institutional change. In this context, dialogue grounded identity in collaboration. Based on my insider's observation, participants often engaged in an ongoing dialogue among peers within the networks of relational trust. Those who were affiliated within the circle of trust get accessed to critical information. Others, who were not part of the so-called circle of trust, engaged in continuous inquiries until they were able to secure the validation. This dynamics suggested that communication during change involved negotiated form of belonging and influence. Identity served as the identifying mark for those whom can be accepted to the circle of trust.

Sensemaking as an Iterative Activity. *Sensemaking as an Ongoing Engagement* captured the participants view of leadership transition as a continuous process of dialogue, reflection, and evaluation. They emphasized that making sense in a transitional environment demands adaptive learning which requires adjustments in meaning creation.

The theme is supported by two sub themes - *Continuous Reflection and Action*, and *Collaborative Inquiry and Peer Discourse*.

Continuous Reflection and Action. A reflective approach to managing change was through constant application of adjustments and assessments. Further, another strategy was adaptability to evolving institutional situation. Participants emphasized these views,

I learn more and more about planning tools like SWOT and gap analysis as I use them more. I think of change as something that happens over and over again and needs to be looked at again. (P1)

...change is a process that never ends, so I need to change how I deal with it, especially when I find out new things. (P2)

I look at the transformation as a continuing activity and that I need to develop adaptability to the ongoing change. My approach is dependent on the kind of challenges and opportunities that come along with change. (P5)

I understand that the leadership transition is by nature dynamic. I need to be open to the changing situations. (P7)

These views showed the participants understanding of leadership transition. They understood that the process was evolving and that it required constant adjustments to changing dynamics of the transition. This understanding also allowed them to become more resilient despite the uncertainty.

Collaborative Inquiry and Peer Discourse. Participants believed that leadership transition needs peer communication and collective inquiry to clear the uncertainty. They made use of communication networks, these were colleagues within their circle of trust, which filtered and validated information and cues.

As a young faculty member and official, I deal with complexity of the university by working with others and talking to them all the time. (P6)

Conversations with trusted peers help you deal with uncertainty as it comes up. I slowly build a more coherent understanding through discussion. (P10)

I depend on my colleague to help me understand the transformation. This helps me stay up to date and grounded in my understanding. (P12)

They also emphasized the importance of collective inquiry believing that it helps in confirming information. Consulting their colleagues whom they considered as official reference was also important. This means that in uncertain situation trust was significantly valued.

When things are not clear, I ask my colleagues who know more about them. This conversation helps me understand my changing goals and keeps me interested. (P16)

...if I am not sure about something, I talk to people I trust and look for institutional references. (P24)

As uncertainty heightened during leadership transition, participants turned to peer communication to improve their information gathering and validations. As observed, most of the participants relied on officials they can trust in making inquiry. For them, it was the safest way to gather plausible information which they act on.

Foundation of Meaning-making. The theme *Cues as Cornerstone of Meaning Construction* illustrated the participants understanding of emerging cues during transition. For them, major or minor signs constituted significant meaning that explains the ambiguity of leadership change.

The theme is founded on three sub-themes – *Grounding on Structured Communication*, *Informal Cues in Peer Dialogue*, and *Filtering Amidst Cue Saturation*.

Grounding on Structured Communication. Formal communications such as memos, circulars, and policy releases were formal cues used by participants to facilitate comprehension of the leadership transition; informal exchanges were considered secondary in terms of influence to the change narratives. Participants had these views,

... we always wait for the official memo. That's where we start with everything. (P5)

...policies that are clear are not up for discussion. They give us something to hold on to. (P11)

The official rules tell us what we can and can't do. (P19)

...we make sure that our answers match what the university says. (P24)

...even if we talk informally, the signed papers tell us what to do. (P7)

Although formal cues can be relied on for stability and legitimacy during the transition, participants' views showed that it lacked the immediacy of an informal cues. However, policies, memos, and circulars holds institutional importance which usually dismisses speculations among the participants.

Structured communications functions as filters and safeguards that reduces uncertainty, thus forming a unified framework for understanding change. But it should not be disregarded that structured type of cues lacks the actionable nature of informal cues, the reason why participants' make sense in the absence of which.

Informal Cues in Peer Dialogue. Reliance on peer communication and other interpersonal exchanges were sources of cues. At times informal cues were used to substantiate or contest official narratives as participants believed they lack emotional and relational depth.

Sometimes unwritten information have more bearing especially those that can be heard from colleagues during meetings and informal chat sessions. (P2)

..our staff meetings do more than just updates us; they make feedback how the change is going. (P14)

It is not always the circulars that get the point across, sometimes it is the informal conversations. (P18)

Your listen to what others are saying... that's how you make the understanding. (P27)

These suggested that peer-to-peer communication works as filter of interpretation. Participants emphasized discussions in meetings, corridor chitchats, and peer networking were good avenues for evaluating directives. Informal forms of communicative activities allowed them to transform ambiguous directives into a practical and relatable context. Their belief showed informal communication as complementary to official communications.

Based on my insiders' view, it is actually evident that informal interpretive spaces had more influence to decision making. Policies may set the boundary, however it was the cue exchanges within the interpersonal networks that clears up how these limits were experienced, challenged, or accepted.

Filtering Amidst Cue Saturation. Participants saw the transition as an overload of information from multiple sources such as emails, memos, and rumors. Managing this information overload, they try to sort information according to their relevance, reliability, and urgency.

... many information which are coming in such as emails, chats, and memos have to be manage well to determine which one is important. (P10)

There are times when cues in the information do not match, so I make sure to choose those that fits our goals. (P22)

I pay attention to cues that can act on. I put it on hold until I know what it means. (P6)

Some participants emphasized professional experiences as determinant of the relevance of all the information that go with the transition; others were looking at systematized judgment – importance and source - just to be sure.

I know what cues are just noise because of what I have been through before. (P15)

...need to sort messages by how important they are, how relevant they are, and who sent them. (P26)

This filtration approach balances relevance, reliability, and urgency. Data were treated as layered cues where there were information requiring urgent attention, some needed to be verified, and others had to be discarded as they were irrelevant to the transition narratives.

Actionable Truth. The theme *Plausibility as the Pragmatic Truth* argued the participants' reliance on practical and actionable information to make interpretation. Instead of waiting factual information, which usually takes time, they took preference to information providing reasonable explanations permitting quick and timely actions. Even though some participants preferred verifiable data, in an increasing uncertainty, still informal communications were used which provided practical interpretations.

The theme had three sub-themes – *Credibility as Foundation for Action*, *Pragmatism over Accuracy*, and *Credibility Cornerstone of Plausibility*.

Credibility as Foundation for Action. This sub-theme emphasized that participants relied on sources they can trust. From these sources came explanations they find confidence in making actions. Aside from these they also made effort in verifying information to safeguard its reliability. At times, they considered feedback as measures of reliability and legitimacy.

...even when things are not clear, I pay attention to reliable sources and measurable indicators. (P1)

When I make decisions, I put credibility before speculation. (P11)

...before I make any conclusions about change, I make sure to check my sources. (P15)

...stakeholder feedback helps me better understand things. (P25)

I use triangulation to make sure that different points of view are reliable when things are not clear. (P17)

Credibility was perceived as the core of sensemaking. It was clear that participants sought more reliable information to serve as basis for their interpretation and understanding. It determined which cues were worth acting on and provided the surety that decisions were defensible, actionable, and strategically aligned.

They also emphasized trustworthiness as a shared belief. As such, they only believed interpretations and information coming from peers whom they trust. Triangulation was also used to ensure that their actions and decisions were carefully checked.

As an insider, I observed that participants would always referenced credibility in many of their discussions. This form of dependence over trusted cues empowered them to manage ambiguity with ease without losing their alignment with the goals of the institution.

Pragmatism Over Perfection. Participants adopted a pragmatic stance as they managed the uncertainty of leadership transition. They looked at plausibility as a practical solution when decision had to be made under critical and urgent conditions. Some participants had practiced balancing accuracy with the demand of the ambiguous situations implying that they had to be flexible with their approach.

I rely on practical reasoning rather than those unproven assumptions. (P16)

.. making decision based on incomplete but reasonable information is better than waiting for delayed release accurate data. (P5)

I tend to balance credible facts and those which are accurate based the situations. If the situation demands critical decisions, accuracy is important; if not reasonable and timely information ae enough. (P14)

...just becoming more responsive and resilient when facing situations with inadequate information and connect with others to enhance my own interpretation. (P21)

Participants believed that understanding leadership transition demands the adaptative pragmatist approach. Realization had them contemplate that waiting for detailed information presented risks of delay and that plausibility emerged as the acceptable means when urgent actions were needed. The only problem was whether the available information can sustain the needed data to understand the transitional uncertainty despite inadequate details. This perspective presented the idea that leadership change introduced a complex situations required the “good enough” information moving forward.

Plausibility discernment suggested determining when can an actionable information adequate and whether accuracy was non-negotiable. The pragmatist response was not a nonchalant choice but a contextual decision. From my reflexive standpoint, this pragmatic orientation was evident during institutional assessment where decisions had to be made in exigency.

Strategic Credibility. This sub-theme introduced the concepts of trust and acceptance which make interpretations and actions to be relied on by participants during leadership transition. These did not came along with their leadership positions but from the regular alignment of their judgement and action in a specific situation. Participants showing strategic credibility offered interpretations that were plausible, context-sensitive, and responsive to the uncertainty of the leadership transition. As such, they also allowed others to make used of their interpretations as reference for their own sensemaking.

...i prefer information coming from colleague whose judgements are always consistent with factual data. This make them reliable in situations where information seem confusing. (P6)

...narratives passed though must be reasonable enough to be trusted as true, it has to be on point. (P7)

...conversing with more experienced colleague can provide the most practical information which are believable. (P19)

I use triangulation to make sure interpretations are consistent with what is acceptable by many. So I make multiple inquiry from different sources until I am satisfied. (P26)

In these views, credibility became strategic given that participants permitted to be influenced without being constrained by others. It enables them to frame their own conversation with no restraint. This is how collective understanding develops and balance actions during the transition.

Chapter VII

DUAL-LENS SENSEMAKING IN LEADERSHIP TRANSITION

This chapter presents the study from empirical findings to the theorizing of the *Dual-Lens Sensemaking in Leadership Transition* as its main contribution. The discussion is divided into five sub-topics - *Cross-Property Patterns of Sensemaking*, *Dual-Lens theorizing of Leadership Transition*, *Emergent Constructs of Dual-Lens Sensemaking*, and *Theoretical Implications*. The chapter discussions conclude with the *Practical and Administrative Implications* that describe the study's inputs to the administrative practices in higher education.

Cross-Property Patterns of Sensemaking

The results of the study demonstrate a consistent pattern across the seven properties of sensemaking where Complex domain predominantly shaped the interpretative processes of university middle managers during leadership transition. Both quantitative and qualitative data affirmed these results. Strong consensus on adaptation, collaboration, and plausibility was highlighted in the quantitative results. These results indicated preference towards strategies prioritizing coherence, flexibility, and actionability than factual accuracy of information among middle managers. Despite the observed differences in terms of degree across properties, the overall pattern showed strong collective narrative toward adaptive approaches to understand leadership transition.

The quantitative results were expanded by the qualitative narratives. Sensemaking properties such as identity construction, retrospection, enactment, and plausibility were mostly enacted within the complex domain. A situation where uncertainty was more defined and social interactions shaped the condition for action.

For middle managers, identity construction was formed and maintained through communication, retrospection was through the reconstruction of relevant and related past experiences, enactment was the deliberate collaborative engagements to create perceive environments, and plausibility was the recognition and acceptance of workable interpretations of the uncertain situation. These understanding confirm that collaborations and situational adjustments are practically valuable to sustain meaning creation.

The interpretive analysis of leadership transition's understanding surfaced seven interconnected themes: *Identity as an Adaptive Self*, *Retrospection as Negotiated Reality*, *Situated Intentional Action*, *Collaboration through Dialogue as Core of Sensemaking*, *Sensemaking as an Ongoing Engagement*, *Cues as Cornerstone of Meaning Construction*, and *Plausibility as the Practical Truth*. The themes suggested that middle managers interpreted leadership transition as a context where they need to maintain adaptability, continuity, and alignment with the institution.

The collective nature of sensemaking emphasized the creation of shared meaning as middle managers engage in interaction among each other and developed network of relationships where trust and legitimacy became the core of strategic credibility.

The cross-property patterns exposed leadership transition as a negotiation of interpretations among middle managers. They constantly reconstruct, recalibrate, and revalidate these interpretations based on credibility. Sensemaking required favorable context and relational dynamics to stabilized.

The next section draws from empirical integration to conceptual theorizing to demonstrate how the dual-lens framework explains the reciprocal interplay of context and process.

Dual-Lens Theorizing of Leadership Transition

The results show that understanding sensemaking during leadership transition was effectively explained through the integration of Weick's sensemaking properties and Snowden's Cynefin framework. Each lens was analytically significant, but collectively both elucidated how middle managers engaged in sensemaking as an interpretative process navigating through evolving contextual conditions.

The Cynefin lens defines the context for sensemaking where Complex domain was the most common situation where change was understood across all seven properties. Interpretation of leadership change does not depend on rules (Clear) or technical expertise(complicated). Middle managers interpret uncertainty of leadership change through continuous dialogue and adaptation. Domain shifts supported this perspective. The definitive anchors like memorandums provided only temporary stability revealing their insufficiency. Intricate reasoning rooted in expertise evolved into adaptive practices and chaotic experiences, initially based on personal values, shifted into complex enactments as collaboration and dialogue helped achieved coherence.

The interpretive process used Karl Weick's sensemaking lens where identity was framed as a result of collaborative activities, retrospection was used as adaptive alignment to the transition, enactment was used to produce a cohesive environment during the transition, collective understanding of the transition was facilitated by social activity, trust was the reference for cues about the transition, and plausibility gained legitimacy based on strategic credibility.

The approach using the dual-lens showed the complimentary relationship between context and process. In this case, the activation of the sensemaking properties was determined by context; while the interpretive processes changes how

these contexts should be understood. Retrospection showed these exchanges as it was initially located in the Clear or Complicated domain; plausibility also showed this relationship as it was used to maintain strategic credibility. These results confirmed that making sense during leadership transition was a never-ending struggle between uncertainty and interpretive actions to create an acceptable and credible interpretations.

This theorizing discussion surfaced the emergent and adaptive characteristics of sensemaking. Contexts were classified by the Cynefin framework; however, it does not explain how interpretation varies within each context. Just the same, Weick's sensemaking draws the interpretation but falls short in differentiating across contexts. Combining these two approaches bridges the gap mentioned. In this case, to understand leadership change in an academic environment, a dual-lens framework provides an in-depth perspective.

Building on this theorizing, the next discussion presents the emerging constructs extending sensemaking as a theoretical and practical frameworks in managing leadership change.

Emerging Constructs of Dual-Lens Sensemaking

The integration of quantitative breadth and qualitative depth through the dual-lens approach generated emergent constructs that extend the theoretical perspectives of sensemaking. These constructs explain how middle managers manage ambiguity and transformed it into continuity, resiliency, and credibility. Each construct is situated within a specific sensemaking properties as the foundational perspective and expanded using the insights from the Cynefin framework.

Identity Resilience through Collaborative Adaptation. Middle managers construction of identity through collaborative engagements was an adaptive approach towards leadership transition and that the concept of professional self was maintained using communicative activities. Results showed a strong consensus on identity and institutional alignment suggesting that middle managers anchored their self-concept through the institution's goals.

According to Weick (1995) identity is significant to sensemaking as individuals used it as reference to understand their environment. However, Weick primarily framed identity as an individual's cognitive tool. This study expanded this view by emphasizing collaborative adaptation to which middle managers' identity was maintained and reframed through dialogue.

Retrospection as Adaptive Alignment. Retrospection was used by middle managers to understand the uncertainty of leadership transition. Their past institutional experiences were reinterpreted to align with the change situation.

Weick argued that retrospection is a process where individuals contemplate their prior experiences during uncertainty. This definition put forward the reflective nature of the process. In contrast, this study conceptualized retrospection as a mechanism to maintain alignment with the new goals and directions of the institution. In other words, prior experiences were used as framework to interpret emerging complexities instead of simply reflecting on the past.

Participatory Enactment of Sensible Environments. The study framed enactment as an intentional collaborative process of establishing an environment. In shaping the environment middle managers established the

concepts of mentorship and collaboration as valuable inputs to shaping the context.

On the other hand, Weick (1995) conceptualized enactment as performative focusing on the interaction between action and environment. However, it does not imply the collaborative and participatory nature of the concept. This study expanded this concept by adding participatory enactment with dialogue and collaboration as the key elements. The extended definition incorporates a participatory environment promoting resilience and collaboration in a leadership transition.

Social Activity as Emotional Support. Social activity was the center of meaning construction where relational trust was developed and emotional support sustained. Narrative accounts clearly delineated communication, dialogue, and feedback as vital in understanding leadership transition. This was strongly corroborated by the empirical results showing strong agreement with the motion on collaboration and interaction.

In his version, Weick (1995) argued that since sensemaking is inherently social; it is grounded in interaction and interpretive activities. It is however more individually cognitive rather than emotional. The present findings expanded this conceptualization by emphasizing social interaction as collaborative combining cognition and emotions. The emotional dimension stressed belongingness, trust, and resiliency during uncertainty. It highlights communication as an interpretive tool and at the same time as an emotional support mechanism.

Ongoing Process as Iterative Engagement. The findings had consistently characterized the recurring nature of sensemaking. This present leadership transition as a continuing process of generating reflection and

reframing of interpretations. The quantitative data demonstrated the most robust consensus on the assertion of continuing process. The agreement indicated a widespread recognition that change is continuous rather than fragmented.

Weick (1995) described sensemaking as an ongoing process as well; however, his focus was more on continuity rather than on the cycles of adaptation. The findings of the study refined this theoretical assumption by framing the continuous process as an iterative engagement. This means that the ongoing process of making sense keeps on occurring until an actionable interpretation was achieved. The construct redefined continuing sensemaking as a systematic cycle of recalibration of interpretation.

Situated Cueing Based on Context. Cues were perceived as contextual signals derived from relational trust and adaptive interpretation. The narratives of middle managers showed that they looked at leadership behavior, institutional priorities, and communication dynamics as cues but makes re-interpretation depending on the situation. On the other hand, there were variations in terms of dependence to formal indicators. This means that cues alone do not provide interpretive stability; thus, they necessitate contextualization.

Weick (1995) argued that cues are fragments selectively extracted to frame interpretation. His view emphasized the process of filtering but did not sufficiently account for how cues are relationally redefined. The present study advances this property into the construct of situated cueing where signals gain meaning only through interaction and contextual negotiation. This expansion highlights that cues were collectively constructed into actionable patterns of interpretation based on contextual conditions.

Plausibility as Form of Strategic Credibility. In the absence of factual truth, plausibility was positioned as the practical entry point directing action. Middle managers narratives emphasized that acceptability, timeliness, and relational trust were far more important than factual accuracy in enabling institutions to stability under the conditions of uncertainty. Results from the quantitative data substantiated this view indicating strong consensus that consistency and functionality were valued above absolute accuracy.

Plausibility was contextualized by Weick (1995) as the principle of “*good enough*” interpretations driving individuals to make actions. The results of the study broaden this notion to include the concept of strategic credibility where plausibility was about trust, validity, and coherence. This expansion redefines plausibility as a pragmatic and reputational motivating actions and reinforces trust during leadership transition.

Table 8. Emerging Constructs of Dual-Lens Sensemaking

Construct Name	Core Idea	Sensemaking Properties	Weick’s View	Expansion to Theory
Identity Resilience through Collaborative Adaptation	Identity sustained through collaboration, mentorship, and institutional alignment.	Identity Construction	Identity is formed as individuals retrospectively make sense of experiences - "how can I know what I think until I see what I say?" Identity is both input and outcome of sensemaking.	Identity is sustained through dialogue and collaborative adaptation.
Retrospection as Adaptive Alignment	Re-interpretation of past experiences as an adaptive mechanism towards the new realities.	Retrospection	Recollection of past experiences which allow individuals to reflect on their individual experiences.	Retrospection as framework to sustain alignment and interpret emerging complexities for adaptive purposes.
Participatory Enactment of Sensible Environments	Environments intentionally co-created through collective	Enactment	Individuals “act into” their environment to make sense of it. Social interaction	Enactment is participatory and collaborative, generating resilience

	engagement and mentoring.		helps reduce equivocality.	and co-ownership of institutional direction.
Social Activity as Emotional Support	Dialogue as both interpretive and emotional support mechanism in uncertainty.	Social Activity	Sensemaking is inherently social, grounded in interaction and shared interpretation .	Communication is dialogic, recursive, and affective, reinforcing belonging and trust during transition.
Ongoing Process as Iterative Engagement	Change normalized as cyclical reflection, feedback, and recalibration.	Ongoing Process	Ongoing sensemaking as continuous activity.	Ongoing process reframed as iterative cycles of adaptation and feedback sustaining institutional resilience.
Situated Cueing Based on Context	Signals interpreted relationally within institutional dynamics, not as static indicators.	Extracted Cues	Individuals reduce ambiguity by extracting salient cues. Sensemaking favors plausibility (coherence) over factual accuracy.	Cues are situated and developed through interaction based contextual and relational interpretation.
Plausibility as a Form of Strategic Credibility	Sufficiency and trust prioritized over accuracy to sustain legitimacy and enable timely action.	Plausibility over Accuracy	Plausibility as “good enough” coherence over factual precision.	Plausibility is based on strategic credibility requiring trust and institutional coherence during uncertainty.

Theoretical Implications

The emerging constructs refined and expanded the previous theoretical understanding of sensemaking when applied to leadership transition in higher education institution.

The use of Cynefin framework and Sensemaking theory as an integrated lens suggested that sensemaking cannot be understood simply as cognitive or individually driven activity. Instead, it should be understood as a collaborative activity and as an iterative process where interpretations or understanding are continuously revised and negotiated as contextual situations keep on changing.

These emerging constructs developed the *Dual-Lens Sensemaking Framework* in understanding higher education leadership transition. The framework

illustrate how sensemaking process was used to understand the uncertainty of leadership transition in an academic context.

Practical and Administrative Implications

The findings of the study highlight the vital role of middle managers as interpreter of leadership transition in higher education. Their sensemaking strategies shows that administrative stability was based on participatory and dialogic processes rather than pure hierarchical directives.

For administrative practice, this necessitates the institutionalization of consultative platforms, mentoring systems, and feedback mechanisms that empower middle managers to collaboratively generate meaning. By incorporating reflective practices into organizational routines, such as systematic post-transition evaluations and after-action analyses, universities can convert uncertainty into opportunities for learning, adaptation, and resilience.

Results further emphasized the adoption of leadership strategies responsive to the rapidly evolving context of organizational change. This as the findings indicated that middle managers often traversed varying shifts across domains of complexity, privileging coherence and plausibility over absolute accuracy. For practice, this puts emphasis on transparent communication to establish consistent narratives so as to minimized disconnect and mistrust during change situation. This implies that administrative practices in higher education should move towards a reflective governance to maintain institutional coherence while thriving amidst any uncertainties

Chapter VII

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study examined the sensemaking process of middle managers during leadership transition in a Philippine state university, employing a dual-lens analysis based on the sensemaking theory and the Cynefin framework. The research specifically sought to (1) measure the extent of middle managers' engagement in sensemaking processes during leadership transition, (2) examine how contextual conditions prompt middle managers to make sense, (3) explore middle managers' interpretation of leadership transition, and (4) identify emergent constructs that extend sensemaking framework.

Summary

This study examined middle managers' sensemaking during institutional leadership transition. This type of transition often generates uncertainty and ambiguity; yet, there is a paucity of understanding how academic middle managers construct meaning, sustain coherence, and strategically adapt in these context. To fill this gap, this study explored the dynamics of sensemaking by analyzing middle managers engagements with the transitions, examining the contextual conditions of sensemaking, their interpretations of the point of ambiguity, and the identification of theoretical constructs extending the appreciation of the sensemaking framework.

The research employed a convergent parallel mixed-methods design which integrated both quantitative and qualitative approaches. Twenty-six administrative officials took part in this study. Their job made them as the mediating link between the head of the institution and the stakeholders. The data collection utilized a structured survey to assess sensemaking engagements and contextual responses,

complemented by open-ended questions providing qualitative insights. Descriptive analysis was used for the quantitative data, while quantitative data were analyzed using narrative and thematic analyses guided by the Cynefin framework and sensemaking theory. The approach of combining these methodologies enabled a dual-lens examination of the contextual conditions and interpretative processes which help in a comprehensive understanding of the sensemaking processes during leadership transitions.

The results showed that university middle managers were consistently making sense throughout the seven properties of sensemaking. Quantitative results indicated that the average mean scores exceeded 5.5, while the modal responses being 6 and 7. This means that there was a strong agreement that sensemaking methods were valuable during leadership transition. Plausibility, retrospection, and ongoing process were noted as the most prominent among the seven properties. Qualitative narratives corroborated these patterns demonstrating that engagement was sustained through dialogue, mentoring, relational trust, and feedback. Middle managers generally characterized sensemaking not as an individual cognitive activity but as a dialogic and social practice frequently adjusted in response to developing cues.

The examination of contextual conditions revealed that the Complex domain of the Cynefin framework served as the major context of interpretation. The episodes of sensemaking activity were frequently initiated in Clear, Complicated, or Chaotic contexts - anchored in regulations, technical expertise, or value-oriented responses – but ultimately achieved stability in Complex situations where collaboration and relational adjustments fostered practical coherence. Domain shifts were evident across sensemaking properties: identity often commenced with role-based grounding in the Clear domain, subsequently transforming into collective enactments in Complex

contexts; retrospection sometimes depended on technical proficiency in the Complicated domain before advancing to adaptive reinterpretations of institutional memory; and cues initially regarded as static were contextualized within relational networks.

Seven themes were identified in the findings. These themes were *Identity as an Adaptive Self*, *Retrospection as a Negotiated Reality*, *Situated Intentional Action*, *Collaboration through Dialogue as Core of Sensemaking*, *Sensemaking as an Ongoing Engagements*, *Cues as Cornerstone of Meaning Construction*, and *Plausibility as the Pragmatic Truth*.

The theme *Identity as an Adaptive Self* contextualizes professional duties within strategic and ethical responsibilities, perceiving the transition as a measure of adaptation and integrity rather than a disruptive institutional change. *Retrospection as Negotiated Reality* demonstrated that prior reforms and persistent personal beliefs provided clarity and stability; however, past institutional inconsistencies cultivated a cautious optimism toward the new administration. Middle managers' sensemaking exhibited *Situated Intentional Action* where they regarded themselves as active co-creators of institutional direction and influenced results through deliberate initiatives, accountability, and continuous participation. *Collaboration through Dialogue as Core of Sensemaking* stressed that dialogue and peer networks help clarify cues and reaffirm commitments, which leads to shared meaning. *Sensemaking as an Ongoing Engagement* emphasized that the transformation was not a one-time event but a cycle that required thinking, adjusting, and collective inquiry. The theme *Cues as Cornerstone of Meaning Construction* highlighted the value of formal communications and informal interactions with middle managers filtering its credibility and relevance to establish organizational consistency. *Plausibility as the Pragmatic Truth* stressed how

middle managers prioritizes practical, credible and actionable narratives over accuracy.

Cross-property convergence further demonstrated that sensemaking functioned as an integrated system. Identity was consistently redefined through retrospection; enactment was maintained through participatory dialogue; extracted cues were filtered through trust networks; and plausibility ensured institutional stability through actionable narratives. Middle managers perceived leadership transition as a cyclical negotiation of meanings during which they are recalibrated, revalidated, and recreated when new cues emerge.

The patterns mean that sensemaking during leadership transition worked as an adaptative strategy characterized by dialogic, relational, and recursive elements. Weick (1995) argued that sensemaking is an ongoing and socially based activity. This claim was supported by the strong engagement of middle managers across all seven properties. The importance of the Complex domain supports Cynefin's idea that when things are uncertain, individuals need to work together and come up with new ideas rather than relying on rules or technical solutions. Domain shifting as observed demonstrated that initial dependence on structure and expertise evolved into relational negotiation and adaptive alignment. This only proved that sensemaking was maintained through repeated recalibration.

The newly developed constructs - identity resilience as a collaborative adaptation, retrospection as adaptive alignment, participatory enactment of sensible environment, dialogic social activity as collective meaning-making, ongoing processes iterative engagement, situated cueing based on context, and plausibility as a form of strategic credibility - expanded the theoretical assumptions of Karl Weick's Sensemaking theory with the integration of the interpretive dimensions within the

Cynefin contextual framework. These constructs showed that middle managers keep situations stable, trustworthy, and consistent using participatory, communicative, and credibility-oriented practices. In this framework, sensemaking served as a tool of organizational resilience where uncertainty was transformed into a collective understanding.

The findings framed sensemaking in higher education leadership transition as cyclical and adaptative. Combining sensemaking theory and Cynefin framework, the study put forward the idea that sensemaking was activated within a contextual condition other than its cognitive properties. This allowed middle managers sustain organizational coherence, resilience, and credibility through dialogue, collaboration, and strategic plausibility.

The contribution stressed that effective governance during leadership change relies not on static information, but on iterative, relational, and contextually situated sensemaking.

Conclusion

Leadership transitions in higher education often result to new institutional vision, policies, and priorities. However, these changes create ambiguity compelling middle managers to adapt to changing objectives, address communication inconsistencies, and evolving roles. Using a dual-lens analytical framework that integrates Weick's (1995) seven properties of sensemaking and Snowden and Boone's (2007) Cynefin framework, the study explains the interpretive tendencies and contextual conditions that characterize leadership transitions. This highlights the function of middle managers in maintaining institutional coherence and preserving trust as they guide institutional members through uncertainty and change.

Extent of middle managers' engagement in sensemaking

The findings revealed that middle managers steadily showed high levels of engagements across the seven properties of sensemaking. The results showed that most of them agreed that sensemaking strategies were very important in dealing with the uncertainty that comes with leadership transition. Plausibility, retrospection, and ongoing process appeared as the most significant properties, suggesting preference towards coherence and actionable realities over factual accuracy. This aligns with Weick's claim that sensemaking gives more value on plausibility over accuracy to make sure organizations function continuously despite inadequacy or lack of information. Plausibility suggests that middle managers valued the creation of cohesive narratives to maintain trust and authority. Retrospection is also equally important where past experiences and institutional memory are examined to make an informed decisions by using an adaptive rather than a structured approach. The ongoing process stressed that sensemaking was a continuous process of negotiated meaning rather than a one-time event. These results highlight the stabilizing role of middle managers amid uncertainty. This corroborates Maitlis and Christianson's (2014) claim that sensemaking is not episodic rather enduring and socially sustained.

Contextual conditions prompting sensemaking

The use of the Cynefin framework enabled the research to assess how middle managers evaluated contextual conditions as a starting point to sensemaking. Findings shows that sensemaking usually commenced in Clear, Complicated, or Chaotic contexts and stabilizes within the Complex domain. This illustrates that middle managers acknowledge the limits of rule-based and expert-driven solutions. They also favor collaboration, emerging strategies, and adaptive negotiations to make sense. Domain shifting is also evident. Identity construction, for instance, usually commenced

with rule-defined roles in Clear context but evolved toward to collective enactments in Complex contexts where collaboration was necessary. Retrospection sometimes utilized technical expertise in the Complex domain but shifted to adaptive reinterpretations that aligned past learning with present need. Fragmented signals, which are first extracted as cues, are considered significant only when filtered through trust networks. This condition highlights that middle managers assessed contextual conditions, modified their strategies, and utilized communicative practices to maintain institutional alignment. These validated Snowden and Boone's (2007) argument that complex situations necessitate emergent responses rather than procedural problem-solving.

Interpretation of leadership transition

The reflexive thematic analysis identified seven themes: *Identity as an Adaptive Self*, *Retrospection as a Negotiated Reality*, *Situated Intentional Action*, *Collaboration through Dialogue as Core of Sensemaking*, *Sensemaking as an Ongoing Engagement*, *Cues as the Cornerstone of Meaning Construction*, and *Plausibility as the Pragmatic Truth*. Collectively, these indicate that middle managers interpreted leadership transition as uncertain which requires strengthening of institutional coherence. They contextualized professional *Identity as an Adaptive Self* within institutional objectives and ethical values which interprets the transition as a measure of adaptability and integrity rather than a disruption. This echoes Gioia and Thomas's (1996) assertion regarding the significance of identity work in organizational change. *Retrospection as a Negotiated Reality* emphasizes institutional stability and continuity while recollections of past inconsistencies triggers cautious optimism extending Weick's (1995) concept of retrospection. *Situated Intentional Action* is evident in

proactive contributions and accountability, consistent with Maitlis and Christianson's (2014) idea of sensemaking as both interpretive and action-oriented. The findings indicate that the leadership transition is constantly negotiated among middle managers which corroborated Balogun and Johnson's (2004) claim that middle managers are valuable interpreters of organizational changes.

Similarly, leadership transition is also perceived as dialogic, iterative, and pragmatic. *Collaboration through Dialogue as the Core of Sensemaking* is interpreted as important in evaluating assumptions and reinforcing individual commitments. This idea reflects Maitlis's (2005) emphasis on the social aspect of sensemaking. *Sensemaking as an Ongoing Engagement* emphasized the cyclical nature of transition which aligned with Weick, Sutcliffe, and Obstfeld's (2005) conceptualization of sensemaking as continuous and recursive. Both formal and informal cues are regarded as essential indicators to be assessed for credibility and relevance, expanding Snowden and Boone's (2007) Cynefin paradigm, which highlights contextual cues in the management of complexity; however their views did not emphasize filtering cues as mechanism to manage credibility and relevance. *Plausibility as the Pragmatic Truth* put forward the pragmatic orientation of middle managers who favored credible and actionable narratives over absolute accuracy. This findings affirmed Weick's (1995) assertion that plausibility serves as effective sensemaking.

Emergent constructs extending sensemaking framework

The dual-lens analyses generated new constructs which enhanced and expanded sensemaking theory. These constructs include: *Identity Resilience as a Collaborative Adaptation*, *Retrospection as Adaptive Alignment*, *Participatory*

Enactment of Sensible Environments, Social Activity as Emotional Support, Ongoing Process as Iterative Engagement, Situated Cueing Based on Context, and Plausibility as a Form of Strategic Credibility. Each constructs represent a refinement of Weick's sensemaking properties, embedding them within Cynefin's contextual conditions, to produce a deeper understanding of organizational behavior during uncertainty.

Identity resilience as a collaborative adaptation argues that professional identity is reconstructed through collective engagement. *Retrospection as adaptive alignment* stresses that past experiences are reinterpreted during uncertainty. *Plausibility as a form of strategic credibility* emphasizes that creating credible narratives involve not just personal alignment but also having institutional influence among stakeholders. These constructs conceptualized sensemaking as interpretive and strategic at the same time.

These findings show that sensemaking in the context of leadership transition is viewed as a recurring, communicative, and adaptive process. Middle managers engage extensively in sensemaking, and assessed contextual conditions with sensitivity to complexity. This allow the generation of emergent constructs that expanded the theoretical scholarships of sensemaking framework. Effective governance during leadership transition is not dependent on structured protocols so much so technical expertise. It is sustained through the capacity of middle managers to engage deeply in sensemaking and interpret contextual conditions. Integrating sensemaking properties with Cynefin's domains, the study advances both theoretical refinement and practical leadership practice during leadership transition.

Recommendations

Drawing from the findings that middle managers engage extensively in dialogic and adaptive sensemaking, prompted by contextual conditions with predominance on complexity, interpreted leadership transition as collaborative achievement of adaptive sensemaking, and generated emergent constructs that expanded existing theoretical frameworks, the following recommendations are proposed. These recommendations aim to guide future research on sensemaking and also providing higher education institutions with practical directions for strengthening management practices, and cultivating resilience during periods of transition.

Recommendation for Practice

- a. Universities must institutionalize consultative platforms, mentorship programs, and feedback systems that promote open communication and trust. Integrating these procedures will cultivate a culture of collaborative interpretation, facilitating leadership transitions, and improving organizational alignment. The need to establish consistent channels for communication will help middle managers make interpretations reflective of the collective agenda to sustain stability during the change process.
- b. Professional development programs must be designed to enable middle managers in recognizing contextual situations utilizing frameworks such as Cynefin. Training in adaptive leadership, scenario-based planning, and iterative decision-making will enhance their ability to adjust strategies in dynamic conditions. This approach to leadership development strengthen collective institutional resilience.

- c. Higher education institutions must invest in reflective workshops, post-transition evaluations, and interdisciplinary discussions. These activities facilitates the development of organizational memory and encourage the adaptive recontextualization of institutional and individual experiences. By doing so, institution preserve critical knowledge from prior transitions and ensure that insights inform future actions.
- d. Communication offices must establish protocols that emphasize alignment, credibility, and stakeholder participation, while assisting middle managers in developing narratives that are internally consistent and externally justifiable. These approaches help build institutional trust and credibility during leadership transitions and ensure that communications align with internal objectives and external expectations.
- e. Management frameworks must be reconfigured to emphasize adaptability, collaborative decision-making, and ongoing recalibration as core concepts. Combining these ideas will help establish the central principle in higher education management. This will make sure that leadership transitions are viewed as opportunities to strengthen organizational stability rather than as a disruptions.

Recommendation for Future Research

- a. Future research must explore sensemaking in both public and private universities/colleges through comparative studies that would explain how distinct institutional environments influence adaptive practices.

- b. Leadership changes must be examined over time to enable researchers track the change, stability or transformation of sensemaking over several leadership transition.
- c. Future research must explore the idea using ethnographic observation and quantitative modeling to show how middle managers construct meaning in real time while considering structural trends influencing how they make their interpretations.
- d. Researchers must explore intersections with other theoretical perspective, such as complexity leadership, organizational learning, or resilience theory, by applying these frameworks alongside sensemaking to explain institutional responses to uncertainty more comprehensively.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Summary of Codes and Themes

Themes	Definition	Sub-themes	No. of Codes
Identity as an Adaptive Self	illustrates how participants formulate their professional identity during institutional transformation by persistently negotiating their responsibilities through structure, agency, and adaptation	Role and Institutional Alignment	21
		Enactment through Intention	22
		Relational Adaptation and Value-based Sensemaking	11
Retrospection as Negotiated Reality	illustrates how participants utilize past experiences to remain anchored amid institutional change. Retrospection functioned as both a guide and a reflection, aiding them in comprehending the present while remaining true to their identities as officials	Strategic Clarity through Reflection	6
		Guarded Retrospection as Caution	16
Situated Intentional Action	captures how participants make sense of institutional transformation through intentional engagement, relational identity construction, strategic reflection, and sustained participation.	Enactments by Intentional Action	11
		Sustained Engagement	19
Collaboration through Dialogue as the Core Sensemaking	illustrates how meaning is co-created through collective communication that facilitate comprehension, adaptation, and strategic coherence	Communication as a Shared Activity	25
		Dialogue as a Retrospective Process	8
		Professional Self as Outcome of Collaborative Dialogue	32
Sensemaking as an Ongoing Engagement	pertains to the ongoing, cyclical process by which participants evaluate and reinterpret institutional transformation across time	Continuous Reflection and Action	23
		Collective Inquiry and Peer Dialogue	12
Cues as Cornerstone of Meaning Construction	defines how individuals engage with both structured and emergent signals to manage ambiguity, construct meaning, and guide decision-making	Grounding on Structured Communication	9
		Informal Cues in Peer Dialogue	5
		Filtering Amidst Cue Saturation	24
Plausibility as the Pragmatic Truth	illustrates how participants depend on credible, actionable, and contextually relevant narratives to comprehend change. Instead of pursuing absolute certainty, they participate in adaptive, reflexive, and socially integrated modes of sensemaking.	Credibility as Foundation for Action	25
		Pragmatism Over Accuracy	14
		Credibility as Cornerstone of Plausibility	16

